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Antonymy in the Language

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Abstract: *Antonyms and their types. The use of antonyms in artistic speech. Antonymy in the language. Antonymic relations. Semantic gradation. Intra-word antonymy.*

Keywords: *Lexicology, antonyms, antonymy, synonymy, semantics, semantic gradation, enantiosemy, correlation.*

Antonyms (gr. anti - vs + onyma - name) are words that are different in sound, having directly opposite meanings: true - false, kind - evil, to speak - to be silent. Antonyms, as a rule, refer to one part of speech and form pairs.

Modern lexicology considers synonymy and antonymy as extreme, marginal cases of, on the one hand, interchangeability, on the other - the opposition of words in content. At the same time, semantic similarity is characteristic of synonymous relations, semantic difference is characteristic of antonymic relations.

Antonymy is represented in the language more than synonymy: only words that correlate on some attribute - qualitative, quantitative, temporal, spatial and belonging to the same category of objective reality as mutually exclusive concepts enter into antonymic relations: beautiful - ugly, a lot - a little, morning - evening, delete - approximate. Words of other meanings usually do not have antonyms; cf.: house, thinking, writing, twenty, Kiev, Caucasus. Most antonyms characterize qualities (good - bad, smart - stupid, native - alien, thick - rare and under.); there are also many that indicate spatial and temporal relationships (large - small, spacious - cramped, high - low, wide - narrow; early - late, day - night); fewer antonymic pairs with quantitative meaning (many - few; single - numerous). There are opposite names of actions, states (cry - laugh, rejoice - grieve), but there are few of them.

The development of antonymic relations in vocabulary reflects our perception of reality in all its contradictory complexity and interdependence. Therefore, contrasting words, as well as the concepts they denote, are not only opposed to each other, but also closely related. The word kind, for example, evokes the word evil in our consciousness, distant reminds us of the near, accelerate - slow down.

Antonyms "are at the extreme points of the lexical paradigm", but between them in the language there may be words reflecting the specified feature to varying degrees, i.e. its decrease or increase. For example: rich - prosperous - poor - poor; harmful - harmless - useless - useful. Such an opposition presupposes a possible degree of enhancement of a feature, quality, action, or gradation (Lat. gradatio - gradual increase). Semantic gradation (graduality), thus, is peculiar only to those antonyms whose semantic structure contains an indication of the degree of quality: young - old, big - small, small - large and under. Other antonymic pairs lack the sign of gradation: top - bottom, day - night, life - death, man - woman.

Antonyms that have a sign of gradation in speech can be interchanged to give the statement a polite form; so, it is better to say thin than skinny; elderly than old. Words used to eliminate the sharpness or

rudeness of a phrase are called euphemisms (gr. ei - good + phemi - I say). On this basis, sometimes they talk about antonyms-euphemisms that express the meaning of the opposite in a softened form.

In the lexical system of the language, one can also distinguish antonyms-converses (Latin conversio - change). These are words expressing the relation of the opposite in the original (direct) and modified (reverse) utterance: Alexander gave the book to Dmitry.- Dmitry took the book from Alexander; the professor takes credit from the intern.- The intern passes the test to the professor .

There is also an intra-word antonymy in the language - the antonymy of the meanings of polysemous words, or enantiosemy (gr. enantios - the opposite + sema - sign). This phenomenon is observed in polysemous words that develop mutually exclusive meanings. For example, the verb to depart can mean 'to return to normal, to feel better', but it can also mean 'to die, to say goodbye to life'.

Enantiosemy causes ambiguity in such statements, for example: The editor looked through these lines; I listened to the divertimento; The speaker made a reservation and under.

According to the structure, antonyms are divided into multi-root (day - night) and single-root (come - go, revolution - counter-revolution). The first form a group of lexical antonyms proper, the second - lexico-grammatical. In single-root antonyms, the opposite of meaning is caused by various prefixes, which are also capable of entering into antonymic relations; cf.: embed - lay out, attach - set aside, close - open. Consequently, the juxtaposition of such words is due to word formation. However, it should be borne in mind that the addition of not-, without- prefixes to qualitative adjectives, adverbs most often gives them the meaning of only a weakened opposite (young - middle-aged), so that the contrast of their meaning in comparison with non-representative antonyms turns out to be "muted" (middle-aged does not mean 'old' yet). Therefore, not all prefixes can be attributed to antonyms in the strict meaning of this term, but only those that are the extreme members of the antonymic paradigm: successful - unsuccessful, strong - powerless.

Antonyms, as already mentioned, usually form a pair correlation in the language. However, this does not mean that a particular word can have one antonym. Antonymic relations allow us to express the opposition of concepts in an "unclosed", multi-part series, cf.: concrete - abstract, abstract; cheerful - sad, sad, dull, boring.

In addition, each member of an antonymic pair or an antonymic series can have its own synonyms that do not overlap in antonymy. Then a certain system is formed in which synonymous units are located vertically, and antonymic units are located horizontally. For example:

smart - stupid to be sad - to rejoice reasonable - stupid to be sad - to have fun wise - brainless to yearn - to rejoice big-headed - headless intelligent - stupid

Such a correlation of synonymous and antonymic relations reflects the systemic connections of words in the vocabulary. The relationship of polysemy and antonymy of lexical units also indicates consistency.

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METHODS AND TECHNOLOGIES OF EDUCATION

➤ lectures;

- case study, Vienna diagram, clusters, theory of inventive problem solving (TRIZ);
- classroom work (practical exercises);
- preparation of presentations;
- preparation of an intelligence card.

Variability of Productivity Indicators in Mutant Cotton Varieties

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Abstract: *In this article, the identification of families and lines with high indicators using the mutagenesis method and single selection in the creation of cotton varieties with high yield and fiber quality, their influence on yield characteristics and the factors of achieving variability are presented. In the course of our scientific research, we have presented data on the results of gamma irradiation productivity and variability in M2 mutant forms (So60 5, 10, 15 cr).*

Keywords: *Selection, mutant, variety, line, family, productivity, variability, trait, gamma ray.*

Introduction. In today's era of rapid development, in the development of cotton in our Republic, using the most modern and advanced methods, the creation of high-yielding cotton varieties that meet world standards is one of the urgent issues, and continuous research is being conducted on this.

Increasing cotton productivity is a very complex task and its solution requires a comprehensive approach. One such method is the physical method. This method is very effective and is widely used by scientists all over the world.

Currently, the development of agroclusters in our republic is one of the most important tasks, and first of all, there is a need for new varieties of agricultural crops that produce high-yielding, high-quality products. First of all, the cotton variety being created should be suitable for the soil and climate conditions of this region, it should ripen quickly, it should be resistant to various factors (diseases, pests, saltiness, drought), and it should be processed and harvested with the help of mechanization.

In this regard, some positive results are being achieved by the scientists of the Scientific-Research Institute of Cotton Selection, Seed Breeding and Cultivation Technologies.

As a result of B.A. Khalmanov's research, new dry seeds of *G. hirsutum* L. species S-9082, Turon, Bukhara-102, Jarqagonon were irradiated with different doses of ^{60}So element gamma rays and have valuable economic characteristics. mutant lines and new varieties (SP-2530, SP-2531, SP-2532) were isolated. [1]

Sh.I.Ibragimov created radiomutant lines RM2, RM4, RM5, RM11 using the light emitted from element ^{60}So in cotton selection, and it was found that their yield was 3.8-13.4 hundredweight/ha higher than non-irradiated hybrid combinations. [2]

In recent years, in most countries of the world, the method of induced mutagenesis has been widely used in the selection of various agricultural crops, which allows to change the signs and properties of plants and obtain new forms (mutants) by influencing plants. K.P. Korolev studied the yield of mutant plants in flax. [3]

By V. Avtonomov and others, the signs of "Verticillium dahlia Kleb damage" were observed and control while in some exposures there is a change of 111.4%, it is stated that no regularity has been determined in this regard. [4]

The main task of the research is to create a variety with high productivity and fiber output, and the Turon variety was selected as the starting material. Dry seeds of the Turon variety were irradiated with gamma rays of So^{60} 5 cr, $M_2 So^{60}$ 10 cr and So^{60} 15 cr, and plants and families with high indicators were selected based on individual selection.

Table 1. Analysis of the variability of a plant productivity marker in M_2 mutant forms (So^{60} 5, 10, 15 cr).

M ₂ mutant forms	K=10g								N	M±m	g	V%
	41-50	51-60	61-70	71-80	81-90	91-100	101-110	111-120				
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 5 cr	2	8	19	9	6	3	1	-	48	70,1±13,6	19,2	27,4
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 5 kr	3	7	21	8	5	2	1	-	47	69,1±13,3	18,8	27,2
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 5 cr	-	2	11	18	13	2	2	1	49	81,1±14,3	20,2	24,9
M ₂ Co ⁶⁰ 5 kr	1	7	7	20	9	5	1	-	50	79,1±13,3	18,8	23,7
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 10 cr	-	3	4	6	16	12	3	2	46	82,1±12,9	18,2	22,2
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 10 cr	4	6	7	19	5	4	3	-	48	69,1±13,3	18,8	27,2
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 10 cr	-	2	5	5	20	7	6	3	48	89,1±11,5	16,3	18,3
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 10 cr	-	4	10	18	7	5	2	1	47	83,1±11,6	16,5	19,8
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 15 cr	3	10	17	9	6	3	1	-	49	69,1±13,3	18,8	27,2
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 15 cr	1	2	9	16	13	2	3	-	46	72,1±12,9	18,2	25,3
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 15 cr	4	6	21	8	6	4	1	-	50	72,1±12,9	18,2	25,3
M ₂ So ⁶⁰ 15 cr	2	3	11	15	9	5	4	-	49	72,1±12,9	18,2	25,3
(St) Namangan-77	-	2	8	19	12	5	1	-	47	77,2±11,1	15,8	20,4

Table 1 presents detailed data on the variability of the growing season of M_2 mutant forms. It was found that the productivity of the plants was in the range of 69.1 g to 89.1 g.

From each irradiated dose 4 variants were obtained: 48, 47, 49 and 50 in 5 cr, 46, 48, 48 and 47 in 10 cr, 49, 46, 49 and 47 in 15 cr plants are taken. The highest indicator was obtained in the variant 3 with 48 plants irradiated at $M_2 So^{60}$ 10 cr, the productivity of plants was in the range of 69.1 g to 89.1 g.

According to the results of the research, the following conclusions were reached: Cotton seed was exposed to 3 doses of gamma rays and various valuable economic traits were changed.

The most positive mutations were detected in medium-fiber cotton in the first and second doses according to the raw material mass, productivity and fiber yield of one plant.

3 different doses of gamma rays showed partial changes compared to the prescribed level..

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Aircraft with Thrust Power and Solar Power Hybrid Power Generation on Runway Advanced Pre-Landing Guidance

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Abstract: Harvesting energy from any source is becoming increasingly important for developing nations. In some places, like airports, natural and renewable energy could help maintain a healthy ecosystem (Runways). Energy harvesting relies heavily on intermittent, weather-dependent wind resources, which introduces significant power quality uncertainty. We'd like to provide an existing concept for the more modern regions with minimization in order to overcome and create power without uncertainty with the improved power quality. Both sides of the runway can have a small wind turbine built to provide the necessary electricity. Power generation has the potential to supply both

clean energy and a crucial metric known as the airplane's touchdown point on the runway (airstrip). About 400 planes a day take off or land at Chennai International Airport. To prevent mishaps and minimise communication lags, pilots must know exactly where the plane will touch down. The integration of cutting-edge technology with a Non-Invasive Network will improve aeroplane landing safety.

Keywords: Pre-Landing, Guidance for aircraft, Thrust, Power and Solar Power, Hybrid Power, Generation on Runway

Introduction

The use of electricity is crucial to modern civilization. Electrical power is generated using both traditional and alternative energy sources [5]. Due to the continuous use of conventional sources, they will vanish from the earth, and the main drawbacks are the contribution to air pollution and global warming; the search for another energy source ends with non-conventional energy sources [6]. As a viable alternative, the growth of renewable energy systems is crucial. Moreover, a single renewable energy system is insufficient to fulfill the energy demand usage of a largely populated crisis [7]. A Runway is a paved, rectangular area at a land airfield that has been cleared for landing and takeoff, as defined by the International Civil Aviation Organization (ICAO) [8]. Man-made surfaces (often asphalt, concrete, or a combination of the two) and Natural surfaces are both acceptable for use as runways (grass, dirt, gravel, ice, or salt) [9]. Runway names range from 01 to 36. The magnetic Azimuth of a runway is often expressed as a tens of degrees. A runway can normally be used in both directions and named for each direction separately: for example, “runway 33” in one direction is “runway 15” when used in another. There is always a difference of 18 between the two (=1800) [10- 15].

Objectives

- The proposed concept Low Power Wind Turbine can installed on both sides of the runway to acquire power during aircraft landing and take off.
- Generally, on runway aircraft, movement will be around 400 KMPH.
- During the movement, great air velocity will occur on the runway, enough to drive a small micro wind turbine to produce power.
- The proposed concept will have a wind turbine, stepdown transformer, rectifier unit, ultracapacitor, lighting system, and an online wireless transmitter.
- The LPWT will be a small double-fed induction generator(DIFG), which can produce 230v output of AC.

Demands for Electricity in Airports

Every aspect of modern existence demands greater energy. Increasing demand for electricity has prompted researchers to make strides in developing a new, sustainable source of energy. All developing nations need to prioritise investing in energy harvesting systems [16-19]. It is more challenging to generate power with all improved power quality from the many alternative energy supplies that have become seasonal, such as solar, wind, and tidal. A major reevaluation of network design and operation procedures was necessitated as a result of the dramatic change toward private businesses making electric power generation one of their business goals as a result of deregulation, open access, and privatisation. Since then, the many companies involved in manufacturing, supply, bulk transmission, delivery (distribution), and metering have become increasingly specialised. While there are numerous obstacles to overcome when researching and developing new forms of alternative power generation, the centralised approach makes maintenance a breeze. In order for network owners to take advantage of emerging potential for alternative power generation, network control and automation will play a crucial role. The airport administration has devised a novel concept for power generation with new area miniaturisation to address the unpredictability of power production [20-27].

Energy Demand Management

Short- and medium-term electricity use are very sensitive to climatic factors. An alternative to generating energy resources at peak times is Energy Demand Management (EDM), also known as Demand Side Management (DSM). When there is a seasonal problem, DSM can be applied in a novel way to the airport runway system in order to balance the intermittent generation from other renewable energy resources [28-33]. The goal of EDM is to better align electricity supply and demand with the requirements of individual businesses and households. The trend in the public and private sectors to generate power for future demands in order to boost energy consumption efficiency runs counter to the goals of energy suppliers. In this scenario, the metro airport is using an alternative energy source to generate electricity for both its own needs and the needs of adjacent homes and businesses. The primary goal of this category of alternative resource is to lower energy needs by employing resources derived from plentiful material inputs. It's important that the environment is kept clean and that the generation method used is safe for all forms of life. Utilities can encourage customers to reduce their electricity consumption through a variety of actions, including those taken in the planning, implementation, and monitoring stages [34-39].

Types of Energy Demand Management

Saving energy means not using any more than necessary to accomplish the same results. In order to achieve this long-term goal, more efficient load-intensive for all customers must be implemented [40].

The expensive cost of adding new generation capacity has led many demand response projects to concentrate on lowering the peak demand for electricity [41-45]. These plans are now under consideration as a means of assisting with the integration of variable renewable energy sources by altering the net load shape (load minus solar and wind generation). To change the timing, level of instantaneous demand, or overall energy consumption, demand response encompasses all deliberate adjustments to power consumption patterns of end-user customers. The term "demand response" encompasses a broad category of responses that can be implemented on the side of the electricity metre by the customer in response to varying conditions in the power grid [46-54].

Organizational power factor and Demand Side Integration (DSI) are both monitored and managed by the dynamic demand concept. Using loads and local generation to aid in network operation/management and enhance power supply quality. By lowering peak demand, DSI can delay the need for new infrastructure. The potential of DSI is contingent on factors such as the frequency and accuracy of information dissemination to consumers, the speed and consistency with which they respond to price signals, and the degree to which end-user equipment and pricing/Contracts are automated [55-63].

Literature Survey

This research [1] uses three approaches to examine the post-landing period. In order to achieve optimal engine performance in accordance with the flying state, HIDE (Highly Integrated Digital Electronic Control) was combined with PCA (Propulsion Controlled Aircraft) to provide the first system for Landing control. Dutch Roll is the second technique, and it is similar to Snake Slithering. The aircraft has around one degree of wiggle room to land safely. The third strategy is called PROTECT (Propulsive Techniques for Emergency Control), and it works by creating the know-how for future aircraft design to use thrust to supplement or replace the flight control system in the event of an emergency. This strategy is employed in conjunction with PCA during the worst-case Capability scenario. Finally, a high sink rate Alarm system called GPWS (Ground Proximity Warning System) should be activated no later than 20 seconds after touching down. Just before the touch-down wing descends rapidly, the pitch and roll continue to oscillate smoothly. The fundamental drawback of this article is that touch-down sites are not automated, despite the fact that scheduling variances have several mitigating effects that could cause runway overshoots and accidents that endanger human lives.

According to the Risk Analysis [2], runway excursions during landing present the greatest risk to aviation. Talk centred on the frequency with which runway mishaps delay passengers. Both takeoff and landing are susceptible to Runway excursions. It's when a plane leaves the runway early, either because it overran it or because it veered off to the side. Various Excursions of the Runway are described, with an emphasis on their efforts to cut down on landing overruns and on the many different safety measures they employ. Aircraft benefit from a tailwind when the wind is blowing in the

direction of flight. The SLG (Safe Landing Guidelines) for determining the speed at which a landing is safe from a height of fifty feet in the air are also covered. The Actual Landing Distance (ALD) begins at a height of fifty feet above the threshold of the runway. FDM (Flight Data Monitoring) keeps tabs on and investigates any new threats that may have arisen throughout the flights.

The new method of electrical power generation from human footsteps is discussed in this research [3]. The generation of power from human waste foot energy and its potential uses are discussed. The force exerted on the ground by human feet can be harnessed and used to power electrical devices. Piezo-electric crystal allows for the conversion of mechanical energy under pressure to electrical energy. Using piezo-electric crystals as an energy-converting material can have significant implications for the power-generating floor. The mechanical energy (stress and strain) is transformed into electrical energy by use of the crystalline piezo-electric crystals. These crystals equally transform the energy produced by the foot's vibrations, tension, or straining force on the floor into electricity that can be utilised to power laptops, mobile phones, and other electrical devices.

For future high-speed, secure, and safety-improving C-Band connectivity, the Aeronautical Mobile Airport Communication System (AeroMACS [4]) was created. This communication channel estimate algorithm requires manual synchronisation of the touchdown point. The runway scenario, including landing and takeoff phases at aircraft speeds up to 60 kn, comprises two key cases. Even at top speeds, the Airborne Scenario remains controllable. Frame timing and fractional frequency Recovery were chosen because they are more computationally efficient than other, more complex schemes developed for the IEEE 802.16 Standard. Effective operation is achieved through the application of OFDM design principles. Finding the landing spot when flying in a Line of Sight (LOS) environment. Additionally, it addresses emerging operational phases in which the plane can communicate with the airport control tower and receive data regardless of its physical location.

Existing System

Runway power management in the current system is handled by a standard power supply, and additional power is needed to make the lighting system functional at night. C-band allows for faster data transfer, however AeroMACS is still required to manually set the landing spot. Aircraft speed analysis between runways from touchdown onwards presents additional challenges [64-71]. Overshooting runways is possible if the plane veers off at an unfavourable angle just before touching down. Accidents and plane collisions could occur if the taxiways weren't properly monitored. The foundation of AeroMACS is the IEEE 802.16 standard, also known as Wireless Worldwide Interoperability for Microwave Access (WiMAX) and tailored for commercial use. A secure wideband wireless communications system is proposed for use on the airport surface to help boost airport capacity and efficiency. An airport's need for communications network connectivity and data capacity rises in proportion to the number and sophistication of its communications, navigation, and surveillance (CNS) systems supporting air traffic management (ATM). The cost of maintaining,

repairing, or replacing CNS infrastructure rises steadily as it ages. Temporary communication solutions are needed during airport construction and unforeseen equipment failures [72-81].

Power for the runway comes from the substation, feeders, and transmission lines just like any other time. Nighttime landing and takeoff require extra power for airport runway airstrip lighting. There will be an energy demand and crisis for industrial and household uses if electricity consumption continues to rise. Many forms of renewable energy production are now only viable at certain times of year due to weather constraints. Alternative energy sources require further development [82-87] (fig.1).

Figure 1: Existing block

Description of the Block Diagram

To power the runway lights, an Embedded Microcontroller is provided rectified electricity from a standard power source. The purpose of the pilot's communication with AeroMACS is to ensure a safe landing. Controlling and measuring aircraft speed and distance, as well as manually monitoring touch-down operations, is the purview of this system [88-93].

Drawbacks of the Existing System

C-band allows for faster data transfer, however AeroMACS is still required to manually set the landing spot. Aircraft speed analysis between runways from touchdown onwards presents additional challenges. Overshooting runways is possible if the plane veers off at an unfavourable angle just before touching down. Accidents and plane collisions could occur if the taxiways weren't properly monitored. More energy is required to power the runway lighting system, which is why it is connected to the regular power grid [94-101]. The current method needs tweaking so that fewer mishaps occur and better options for developing alternate resources may be identified.

Proposed System

Higher-speed C-band communications allow for more precise touch-down point setting in AeroMACS. The analysis of the aircraft's speed between the runways after touchdown presents additional challenges. There is a possibility of overshooting runways due to angle deviations from the touch-down location. It's crucial to keep an eye on the taxiways to prevent planes from crashing into each other. Normal power supply is provided for the runway lighting system, which has a higher energy requirement [102-111]. There has to be changes made to the current system so that there are fewer accidents and better alternatives may be developed (fig.2).

Figure 2: Proposed block diagram of touch-down aviation

Although C-band communications are faster, AeroMACS requires manual adjustment of the touch-down position. It's more complicated to figure out how fast the plane was going between the runways after it touched down. Possible runway overshoot due to angle departure from touch-down point [112-119]. Aircraft collisions and other mishaps are possible if the taxiways are not properly monitored. Extra energy is required for the runway lighting system, which is why it is connected to the regular power grid (fig.3). There needs to be some tweaking of the current setup to reduce the likelihood of mishaps and identify the best strategies for cultivating renewable resources [120-126] (fig.4).

Figure 3: Power generation block diagram of the runway

Figure 4: Flow Chart Design

Touch-down Developments

The touch-down process, which is done manually nowadays, is the biggest concern in the landing. Since human lives are at stake, there is a high potential for mishaps and dangers to occur during aeroplane landings. There was a lot of effort put into trying to find a way to automate the aircraft's landing touch down spot, but it was ultimately unsuccessful [127-131]. Runway safety

measures and communication standards for safe landings require a specific level of public understanding and attention to certain issues.

Landing Techniques

There are two types of landing techniques which are followed in the day-to-day landing; they are,

For landing the Global 5000 in a cross wind, the crabbed approach technique is advised. This is also known as the wings-level technique. This is the method that is taught by Bombardier in their simulator courses. Before beginning the flare, the pilot must perform a drift adjustment to keep the aircraft aligned with the runway centre line, and then, once the flare has begun, he or she must gently apply the rudder to bring the fuselage into a parallel position with the centre line [132-139].

The wing-low technique, also known as the steady sideslip technique, involves the pilot applying opposite rudder and into-wind aileron inputs to counteract drift and keep the plane on the runway's centre line. The possibility of a wingtip strike due to pilot-induced oscillations is raised while using this method. The Global 5000 has a very high dihedral effect, so flying with the wings low is extremely taxing for the pilot. The PF employed the wing-low tactic in this instance. He employed into-wind aileron and opposing rudder to compensate for wind and maintain the plane's centerline alignment with the runway. This cross-controlling not only steered the aircraft away from the threshold, but also deployed the right wing's multi-function spoilers thanks to the automated roll aid component of the flight control system. Reviewing the FDR data, we learned that the spoilers were deployed during the last phase of the approach due to the wing-low strategy. The combination of gusty winds and a shallow approach angle reduced lift, making the aircraft harder to control and increasing the PF burden. The occurrence pilot was familiar with both the crabbed approach and the wing-low technique from their time in the Global 5000 simulator.

Auto Throttle System

The autonomous positioning of the thrust levers in the Global 5000's dual auto-throttle system allows for comprehensive flight regime thrust regulation. The auto-throttle system regulates the ship's speed and thrust automatically. The auto-throttle engage status, operating mode, and faults are all displayed on the primary flight display. The auto-default throttle's mode of operation is airspeed control. In this setting, the system follows the set Mach or active airspeed. On the flight guidance panel, the desired airspeed can be adjusted automatically or by hand. This setting safeguards both high and low speeds. When in flare or landing mode, the retard mode control will automatically bring both thrust levers to the idle position at a predetermined rate. If the go-around mode is activated, the auto-throttle will stay on until landing to provide extra thrust for the manoeuvre. If the landing gear are down and the flaps are higher than or equal to 16 degrees, and the radio altitude is less than 50 feet

above ground level (angle), the retard mode will engage. Bombardier recommends that auto-throttle be used for the whole flight. However, in turbulence or when the thrust levers are hunting, some pilots turn off auto-throttle in an effort to maintain the desired velocity. At any time, the PF can take control and stop the auto-throttle from working. If engine power had been applied properly, the aircraft's low energy state and loss of lift on short final may have been prevented.

Common Approaches And Landing Accidents

Approach and landing incidents most frequently include,

When an aeroplane swerves to the left or right on the runway as it touches down, the manoeuvre is known as a landing veer-off. Environmental elements, human factors, aircraft performance characteristics, and runway conditions are the primary contributors to this.

When a plane doesn't touch down exactly where it's supposed to, it can overshoot the runway, causing serious damage or even a crash. Long, harsh, or quick landings are strongly linked with shaky approaches.

HIDEC

The Highly Integrated Digital Electronic Control (HIDEC) system optimises aircraft performance by fusing the management of an aircraft's engines with that of its air data and flight control systems. The results of the study led to the creation of many control modes that boosted engine thrust with less fuel use. Digital Electronic Flight Control Systems (DEFCS), Digital Engine Electronic Controls (DEECs) installed on the engines, an on-board general purpose computer, and an integrated architecture that allowed all of these parts to "speak to each other" were the mainstays of HIDEC. Both the adaptive engine control (ADECS) and the performance-seeking control (PSC) were digital systems designed for the HIDEC F-15 (PSC). It pioneered the use of a propulsion-only flight control system and a self-repairing flight control system (PCS). Fuel, maintenance, and operational costs for military, commercial, and general purpose aircraft could be reduced by integrating digital propulsion and flight control systems. Crews and passengers alike will welcome the additional cushion in safety afforded by longer engine life and improved engine and flight performance.

PCA (Propulsion Controlled Aircraft)

NASA Dryden designed and tested the Propulsion Controlled Aircraft System (PCA) to aid pilots in making a safe landing in the event of a catastrophic loss to the aircraft's primary flight control components, such as the elevators, rudders, and ailerons. Computer-augmented engine thrust allows pilots to maintain control of the aircraft's pitch, yaw, and roll in the event of a failure in the flight control system. The HIDEC F-15 was used for early testing and demonstrations of the PCA system.

Later, a three-engine MD-11 aircraft was used to test and publicly display the system. NASA has tested the PCA idea on more than a dozen civilian and military aircraft models in flight simulators. Having a failsafe control system in the event of a failure in the primary control system is the most obvious benefit of a PCA system. PCA is useful for more than just increased safety, though. Later developments of the PCA technology resulted in PCA Light and PCA Ultralight, two variants that use the same engine-only control idea as their more expensive counterparts but can be installed in a wider variety of aircraft.

Dutch Roll Method

The Dutch Roll is an approach that makes advantage of damped oscillation in the yaw of a rolling aircraft. Comparable to the longitudinal short-period mode in frequency, but with less damping (Less effective than Horizontal Tail). It's a style of movement characterised by a slithering, snake-like, out-of-phase mix of "Tail-Winging" and rocking from side to side.

PROTECT (Propulsive Technique for Emergency Control)

In the event of an emergency, this procedure can be implemented to control the aircraft utilising propulsion in place of the standard flight control system. This technique is utilised alongside principal component analysis (PCA) in emergency scenarios (fig.5).

Results and Discussions

The C Standards Committee has developed a set of Embedded C language extensions for the C Programming Language to deal with common problems shared by C extensions for various embedded systems. To accommodate unusual characteristics like fixed-point arithmetic, multiple memory banks, and standard I/O operations, nonstandard C language extensions have traditionally been necessary for embedded C programming. The C Standards Committee augmented the C language in 2008 to resolve these problems by establishing an industry-wide benchmark. It has capabilities beyond those of vanilla C, like fixed-point arithmetic, named address spaces, and simple hardware I/O addressing. The main() function, declaring variables and data types, writing conditional statements (if, switch, case), writing loops (while for), writing functions, working with arrays and strings, working with structures and union, working with bits and macros, etc. are all present and accounted for in embedded C. The C Standards Committee has developed Embedded C as a set of C language extensions to address

commonalities between C extensions for various embedded systems. Embedded C has traditionally necessitated nonstandard C language extensions to accommodate unusual features like fixed-point arithmetic, multiple memory banks, and standard I/O. To resolve these problems, the C Standards Committee published a uniform set of guidelines for C implementations in 2008. Fixed-point arithmetic, named address spaces, and primitive I/O hardware addressing are only a few of the features added compared to standard C. The main() function, declaring variables and data types, writing conditional statements (if, switch, case), writing loops (while, for), calling functions, working with arrays and strings, creating structures and unions, manipulating bits, using macros, etc. are all present and accounted for in embedded C (figs.6 to 7).

Figure 6: Hardware image of the project

Figure 7: Abnormal landing image with graphical representation-1

Conclusion

To establish a green and clean energy harvesting system with the self-powered runway and the automated touch-down zone, the concept is assessed and analysed in depth with the software employed, and it can also be used in metro airports. Pressure and impact from the vibration during landing are converted into electricity through touch-down sensors. Power generated at an airport might be distributed centrally to other commercial and residential users, optimising the use of this alternate source of generation. For the sake of the country's social and safety welfare, this project has the potential to provide a comprehensive solution for the current system through increased efficiency and automation. A nation's development can be gauged by its use of alternative energy sources. Dismally, 85,000 villages in India still do not have power, according to a recent analysis on energy consumption in the country. The standard of living is low across the country. There are 134 airports in India. The Airports Authority of India (AAI) is a government-owned corporation that manages 122 of India's 449 airports and civic enclaves. In 2017, Indian airports served more than 295 million passengers. Much energy may be harnessed by installing an equipment like the "Electric Power Generation Unit from airport runways."

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Issues of Popularization and Popularization of the Performance of the Orchestra of Wind and Percussion Instruments among Listeners

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Abstract: *The article is discovered about the system of performance on wind instruments, the basic functions of the orchestra on wind instruments, achievements and disadvantages of wind and percussion performing instruments.*

Keywords: *Arts of music, orchestra wind instruments, military brass orchestra.*

Looking at the culture of performance in the art of music, we are witnessing that this field has its rich past history root. The art of performing is a fundamental piece of music, and as we explore the stage of its development, it is not difficult for us to realize the possibilities of the current era. String, brass band and percussion instruments in which a number of articles and monographs have been written by instrumentalists and musicians from many countries in the context of Icheri Sheher.

The music of Brass band instruments is considered one of the main genres of musical art. Its rich historical traditions, various means of expression and the importance of artistic performance, as well as theoretical and methodological problems – all this is of objective interest to musicologists, cultural practitioners.

In the development of instrumentation, professional performance, there are a number of musicologists and representatives of the same field who are devoted to theoretical and artistic issues of inflatable and percussive instruments (solo and ensemble performance). There are no general studies devoted to the activities of orchestral teams.

At the moment, such widespread communities have their place in artistic culture, performing various socio-cultural tasks, especially in professional artistic creation. Over the course of several centuries, a number of distinctive aspects of damli orchestral music have been identified: timbre brilliance, dynamic power, special power. We have witnessed that this issue is practically absent in the research process of more deeply covered works. The sources of more interest for our scientific work were the following:

It is S. Levine — "Duxovie instrument V muzikalnoy Kulture", O. Usufning — "Istoriya otechestvennogo ispolnitelstva na dukhovix instrumentax" and — "Methodika obucheniya igre na dukhovix instrumentax" is a compilation of scientific and methodological articles (M., 1964-1976).

To date, we are not mistaken to say that the activities of the orchestra of damli instruments have become significantly faoalized. Currently, in the culture of many countries, colorful marching parades, damli cholgu, based on theatrical performances of their Orchestra their large size festivals occupy a wide place. Also, damli cholgu they orchestras regularly at public holidays, festivals, etc.k.has been participating in the S.Scientific innovation of this study – the formation and development stages of the

performance of the orchestra of damli instruments in Uzbekistan on the basis of our national, artistic culture, which has not been fully studied to date consists of a complete analysis of points.

In addition to objective issues, certain subjective factors also played an important role in choosing the subject of the study. It seems to us that in the environment of professional art studies, damli cholg'u they seem that their music is a little far from attention. At the moment, in some regions, we can observe that this genre is not only artistically perfect, but also viewed at a high level in relation to it. This in turn signals the country's national artistic culture.

Inflatable and tattooed cholg'u they began to enter Uzbekistan mainly from Europe, after the Russian invasion. F. In the organization of a Professional orchestra. Leysek, A.Eichgorn, N.The role of art promoters, such as Mironov, became incomparable.

During that time, the role of the Russian damli Orchestra, which enjoyed the local people with Russian and foreign music, became significant. - The dukhovoy orchestra would give concerts in parks and gardens in summer, and in clubs and circuses in winter. Their repertoire included public songs and dances, as well as excerpts from operas from Russian and foreign countries. Such orchestras existed in most cities of Turkestan-given S.M.In the Wexler article. From this program of orchestras, famous Russian marches, waltzes and Regiments were performed, which were played on folk holidays. One of the siymos who contributed to the opening of the first Uzbek Orchestra in Uzbekistan is Hamza Hakimzoda Niyazi. A.According to Odilov — in his book “history of performance in Uzbek folk instruments”: —Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoziy was the organizer of the first Uzbek damli instruments orchestra in Fergana (1916), a person who trained music amateurs in Instrumental Performance among Uzbek Youth with a special emphasis on musical art in the orchestra.

We are interested in the activities of orchestras of damli instruments during the years of World War II, we can witness that the main Etibar was aimed at introducing works created by Soviet composers during these years.

By the 1950s, the activities of wind instrument orchestras in Uzbekistan had become significant mainly with the growth of amateur teams. By the beginning of the 20th century, there was also a certain level of development in terms of the scope of duties in the performance of the damli instrument orchestra.

At that time, the main duties of the bands of wind instruments consisted of those below:

- 1) participation in official celebrations;
- 2) concert-performance activity aimed at the formation of musical-Marian and artistic taste;
- 3) serving at cultural leisure activities.

Among the tasks assigned to orchestras, their repertoire matter was composed based on a certain direction, that is, in the line of traditional march and dance-pop plays, the works of Russian and foreign composers also took place. Later in the 1960s and first half of the 1970s, the wind instrument was a period of obvious negative twists in orchestral activities. One of the main reasons for this was the issue of social change in society and mass taste. The main reason why the social prestige of the music of inflatable Instruments fell especially in the youth audience was the question of the repertoire, which had become a tradition, having acquired the appearance of uniformity.

In such a case, the question of choosing the right path, that is, of the retention of the performers in the orchestral teams, only the uddabran leaders had time to implement it. They were trying to make it possible for them to play new, contemporary pop music at fast times to suit their orchestral repertoire, which would be of interest to the orchestra's participants. Such a great passion for pop music brought harmony (communities of Pop and wind instruments) in orchestras over time.

Through this, the creative foality of other types of damned orchestras also began to turn to positivity. As a result of the observed changes, amateur orchestras also began to see artistic growth and creative barricade.

In the modern process, damli cholgu they are analyzing the folacy of their orchestra, we must admit that they grew up in terms of artistic performance. It is also gratifying that in many communities there are huge changes in the development of the field, due to the activities of highly qualified leaders, responsible training of several amateur, especially children's teams.

As an example, we can cite a separate exemplary-visual military recreation Orchestra of the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan. This orchestra has been presenting its concert programs in parks and gardens under the open sky in order to promote the exciting weekend of the people of the capital and guests from the annual report concerts. In addition, it is necessary to reach the exemplary- visual military band of the Ministry of internal affairs of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The orchestra team is always on the lookout, relying more on the traditions of nationalism. The band has been performing at regular holiday events throughout the country. Military music occupies an important place in our highly developed land of military art and skill and serves as a powerful tool in uniting the people, educating the spirit of Valor, love for the motherland, and advancing towards new goals.

In conclusion, we will not be mistaken if we say that by today damli cholgu they have significantly activated the activity of their orchestra. Currently, the kata volumetric festivals of Damian instruments are taking a wide place in the culture of many countries, based on colorful marching parades, theatrical performances of bands of Damian instruments. Also, bands of damned instruments regularly perform at public celebrations, festivals, etc.k.has been participating in the.

As an example, we can agree with the Ministry of Defense of the Republic of Uzbekistan a separate exemplary military recreation band. In addition to the annual report concerts, this orchestra has been presenting its own concert programs in open-air parks in order to help residents and guests of the capital spend their weekend in an interesting way. Military music occupies an important place in our highly developed land of military art and skill and serves as a powerful tool in uniting the people, in which Valor, the spirit of love for the motherland is brought up, and in advancing towards new goals.

The task of the science of performance of percussion instruments is to prepare specialists who have the necessary knowledge and skills to work as solo orchestra artists and teachers of music schools in the future. In this regard, the science of performance of stringed instruments should teach performance skills to students, educate them to the extent that they can master musical-artistic tasks, educate the skills of reading music from paper, artistic work and reading-assistant. it is necessary to teach them to work independently on the material.

The percussion teacher is the student's main leader. In their work, it is necessary to bring the learning and education processes to one integrity. Not limited to specialized training, the teacher should develop the student's passion for studying and all aspects of social life, develop his musical interest, explain to him the high social importance of fine arts, guide his general and musical development, It is necessary to cultivate musical taste, to deepen musical-theoretical knowledge, to cultivate high self- demand, creative initiative and sense of responsibility, strong perseverance in overcoming difficulties individually. Damli (percussion) music-instrument performance teacher instills in students love for the art of their homeland, the creativity of the people, old Uzbek-Karakalpak music, and the best essays of Uzbek-Karakalpak songwriters, teaches us to be critical and creative relationship to the heritage of world music culture. The tasks of the professor-teacher are determined by the student's individual characteristics and self-restraint. Because of this, it is necessary for the music teacher to be in constant contact with the teachers of other subjects, parents, to help the student's learning and progress, and to

use the study time effectively. The activity of the teacher, his behavior and personal appearance should serve as an example for students.

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Communicative Model of the Aphoristic Text

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Abstract: *In this article, we tried to explain our findings that the authorization of an aphoristic text, which includes such important features of an aphorism as subjectivity, ambivalence, dynamism of meaning, as well as the hypohyperonymic connection “saying - aphorism, proverb,” makes it possible to distinguish peers. Based on this feature, the image of the author is a prerequisite or interpretation of an aphoristic text of an auto-communicative nature.*

Keywords: *addresser - text – addressee, aphoristic text, phenomenon, image of the author, textual activity.*

As is known, the specific content and implementation of the communicative scheme “addresser - text - addressee” can serve as a criterion for identifying the type of text. To describe this communication model, it is necessary to first consider its components separately.

Let's start with an analysis of the category of the image of the author of an aphoristic text. The image of the author, being a complex phenomenon, is interpreted widely and studied from various points of view in such scientific disciplines as literary criticism, psycholinguistics, semiotics and cultural studies, pragmatology and cognitive linguistics. The problem of studying the author's origin in a literary text became especially relevant in the second half of the 20th century, when the text began to be studied in the established communicative-pragmatic paradigm of scientific knowledge.

Associated with the literary direction of development of the theory of the “image of the author” is the consideration of the reflection of the writer's personality in his work at the level of implementation of a certain author's idea and the subordinate originality of the system of images, plot, composition. The importance of studying the “image of the author” was emphasized by V. Vinogradov. He believed that: “... a work of art can and even should reflect traces of the historical originality of the author's life, the originality of his biography, his style of behavior, his worldview”. In the works of G.N. Pospelov explores the problem of the writer's individual creative style. The author writes: “The artistic content of the works, ..., is an expression of the writer's ideological worldview, his emotional and ideological “vision of the world,” cognitively reflecting the world”.

In Western literary criticism, there was a strong tendency to deny the author, which began in the 20s and lasted until the mid-80s. XX century. As noted by A.Yu. Bolshakov, this crisis was generally overcome by the end of the 20th century. Among the main reasons that determined the “return of the author,” in her opinion, one should name the loss of precise criteria for determining the meaning of a work.

In linguistic works, researchers consider the “image of the author” as a category of text that permeates the structure of a work of art and organizes it as a whole. According to E.A. Goncharova, “...the author is the primary and absolute, text-forming category of any text, including artistic text, determining the definiteness of its sign structure and directing the perception of its sign system, where there are both directly verbally expressed images and images of more complex semantics generated by from the

interaction of linguistic meanings of specific text units with their figuratively associative reinterpretations. Both of them are included in the hierarchical system of other levels of the structure of a literary text (expressive-stylistic, subjective-speech, compositional-plot, compositional-speech, etc.)". As Z.Ya. Turaeva believes, the category of the author's image "... holds the entire work together and determines the function, place and role of each of its components.

In Russian and German-language linguistics, the problem of the author of an aphoristic text has not been specifically studied. In research works, the main emphasis, as a rule, is placed on studying the phenomenon of the special impact of an aphoristic text on the reader. Summarizing the conclusions made in domestic and German-language research works, we can conclude that the communicative task of an aphoristic text is to initiate reflection on what was read in the recipient. Agreeing in principle with this point of view, we consider it necessary to emphasize that the reflection caused by reading the aphorism presupposes a collision of two worldviews. The result of this can be considered some changes in the recipient's individualized picture of the world by filling gaps in it or modifying concepts. The specificity of the aphoristic text can be considered its double relevance: self-knowledge of the individual through knowledge of the world of reality.

A significant number of research works are devoted to the study of the phenomenon of the individualized picture of the world of the author of the text, its dependence on the general model of the world of the era, the influence of coincidence/mismatch of the world picture of the author and the reader on the interpretation process literary text.

In cognitive linguistics, it is customary to distinguish between the concepts of a picture of the world (a model of the world, a conceptual system) and a mental lexicon. According to E.S. Kubryakova, the conceptual system, in contrast to the mental lexicon, which reflects knowledge about lexical units, is interpreted, rather, as a set of concepts or mental representations of various types, that is, not only representations of lexemes. O.L. Kamenskaya defines a conceptual system as a continuously constituted and modified dynamic system of data (ideas, opinions, knowledge) that an individual has. The concept of "picture of the world" of the author and recipient of the text is correlated with what is being developed by V.Z. . Demyankov's concept of "cognitive style". Cognitive style is understood by the scientist as "the preferred approach to solving a problem, characterizing a person's behavior in relation to a number of situations and content areas, not regardless of the intellectual level of the individual, his "competence"". As L.G. Luzina, from the perspective of the producer/author of the text, cognitive style indicates the characteristics of the individual reflective process, the subjective nature of its assessments, the knowledge used and activated in this process, as well as the individual experience of the textual activity itself. In this In a sense, cognitive style is a set of verbally implemented cognitive procedures for processing knowledge, a strategy for processing information and its evaluation. From the point of view of the addressee of the text, cognitive style has to do with awareness of how the text is presented, as well as to a certain predisposition of the recipient to process information in a certain way, to search and remember preferred information. Characteristic of the literary cognitive style is the reader's readiness to reorganize the discourse and switch to the level of increased attention in the processing of literary texts.

It is obvious that the perception of an aphoristic type text presupposes the recipient's readiness to work on inferring information that is missing to interpret the meaning of the text. The deliberate reduction in the amount of explicit meaning-forming information (among other things, ellipsis, aposiopesis; semantic omission), the characterization of the text's referent through opposition (irony, sarcasm) or difficult-to-substantiate similarity ("living" metaphor, modeled subtext) allow us to conclude that in aphoristic texts there is a significant and the Rules of Cooperation are deliberately violated. It seems that this feature underlies the pragmatic impact of the aphoristic text.

Since pragmatics is a modern scientific discipline focused on the subject of linguistic communication (the speaker), most studies of the “image of the author” take into account the achievements of this branch of linguistic knowledge. The authors study “the influence of the author’s pragmatic attitude on the modality of the text”, the relationship between the expressive plan of the text and the pragmatic tasks of speech communication, the possibility of providing a pragmatic and aesthetic impact of the author on the reader through the implementation of his speech creative activity, methods modeling a communicative situation in a literary text, etc.

Significant theoretical results within the framework of pragmalinguistics have been achieved in the study of the addressee of a communicative act. A seminal work in the study of the author-reader relationship is the article by N.D. Arutyunova “The Addressee Factor”. According to the author, “every speech act is designed for a certain model of the addressee. Satisfying the addressee’s presupposition is one of the important conditions for its effectiveness”. In this work, we are most interested in the author’s interpretation of the problem of the addressee of literary texts. The researcher notes the presence of parallelism between a speech act and an artistic prose text, since literary communication, just like everyday human communication, is characterized by such pragmatic parameters as the author of the speech, his communicative attitude, the addressee and the associated perlocutionary effect (aesthetic impact). The author’s idea seems valuable, according to which in a literary text as a special model of communication one can state a number of stylistic devices that violate the rights of the addressee. We are talking about the well-known postulates of P. Grice, which are “the communicative duties of the speaker in relation to the addressee”.

We believe that the exploitation of the Rules of Cooperation is a constitutive feature of aphoristic type texts. An aphoristic text uses all types of “thinking errors” nonsense, indirect depiction, depiction using the opposite, compression of information, use in the literal sense of figures of speech that have lost their direct meaning, etc. The degree of deviation from the “norm” “depends on the author’s intentions towards the intended addressee. The studied material gives grounds to assert that there is a direct relationship between the degree of deviation from the Principle of Cooperation and the addressability of the aphoristic text. The highest degree can be assigned to aphoristic texts of an auto- communicative nature (psychoanalysis, self-knowledge, self-determination).

The next step is a violation of the Rules of Cooperation, associated with the address of the aphoristic text to the recipient (philosophical questions - happiness, freedom, morality, beauty, etc.). For example, F. Nietzsche wrote about his potential reader like this: “Ein Aphorismus, rechtschaffen geprägt und ausgegossen, ist damit, dass er abgelesen ist, noch lange nicht “entziffert”; vielmehr hat nun erst dessen Auslegung zu beginnen, zu der es einer Kunst der Auslegung bedarf... Freilich tut, um dergestalt das Lesen als Kunst zu üben, um Eins vor Allem not, was heutzutage gerade am besten verlernt worden ist - und darum hat es noch Zeit bis zur „Lesbarkeit“ meiner Schriften -, zu dem man beinahe Kuh und jedenfalls nicht „moderner Mensch“ sein muss: das Wiederkäuen.” Finally, the least, but still significant, in comparison, for example, with texts of realistic literature or non-literary texts, the degree of deviation from the Rules of Cooperation is found in aphoristic texts intended by the author to the general public (as a rule, the theme of such aphorisms is political, social, educational or frivolous).

It seems that for a text of an aphoristic type, the most typical is the second of the above options for compliance with the Rules of Cooperation. Apparently, this circumstance makes aphoristic texts “long-lived.”

Let us recall that the Principles of Cooperation were developed by P. Grice to describe the situation of verbal communication, the purpose of which is the most effective transmission of information. The author developed four specific postulates, the observance of which corresponds to the implementation of this principle:

- 1) Category of Quantity (transmitted information)
 - a) “Your statement should contain no less information than required.”
 - b) “Your statement should not contain more information than required.”
- 2) Quality Category:
 - a) “Don’t say what you think is false.”
 - b) “Don’t say anything for which you don’t have sufficient grounds.”
- 3) Relationship category:
 - a) “Be relevant.” (Stay on topic.)
- 4) Method Category:
 - a) “Avoid unclear expressions.”
 - b) “Avoid ambiguity.”
 - c) “Be brief (avoid unnecessary verbosity).”
 - d) “Be organized.”

Since we believe that the purpose of transmitting information from an aphoristic text is to influence the mentality of the addressee, his value picture of the world, a change in which can occur as a result of understanding the content of the aphorism, it is obvious that the initiation of reflection by the addressee is a communicative task of this type of text. Unlike a scientific text, the initiation of reflection in the process of interpreting an aphoristic text is aimed not at understanding the objective picture of the world, but at self-knowledge of the addressee. This feature of the aphoristic text dictates a certain tactics of the addressee: influencing the addressee’s individualized picture of the world through emotions: surprise, curiosity, delight, a range of emotions associated with pleasure, as well as some negative emotions.

What gives the recipient grounds to imply the presence of implicit information? First of all, the correct definition of the text type. And, secondly, an intuitive awareness that the text violates any of the Principles of Cooperation. According to P. Grice, violation of the Principle of Cooperation by the exploitation of any (or several) postulates gives rise to communicative implicature. The author notes the following conditions for the recipient to derive a communicative implicature:

- 1) the conventional meaning of the words used and knowledge of their referents;
- 2) The principle of Cooperation and postulates;
- 3) context of the statement;
- 4) other background knowledge.

However, the brevity of an aphoristic text, measured in any units, does not in itself constitute the essence of the aphoristic type of text. Typical for this type of text is a quantitative disproportion between form and content. The relationship between form and thought, characteristic of an aphoristic type of text, can be defined as the relationship between the tip and the bottom of an iceberg: a significant amount of information important for interpreting the meaning of the text is subject to manipulation. The relationship between the brevity of the form and the informative capacity of an aphoristic text, in our opinion, was best expressed by H. Fricke. The scientist believes that writing briefly does not mean writing little, but writing only what is necessary: writing less than would be NECESSARY .

The ratio of explicit and implicit information in texts of various functional styles and genres is not the same. For an aphoristic text, according to many of its researchers (Wehe 1976, Welser 1986, Lubimova-Bekman 2001, etc.), the priority of implicit information should be recognized as characteristic. The laws of the aphorism genre oblige authors to look for the shortest path to the truth, while avoiding banality and unambiguous expression. Due to the fact that implicit information does not have an explicit verbal constructive expression, effective compression of information becomes possible in an aphoristic text. It was this property of implicit information that F. Nietzsche used when creating his aphorisms: "...mein Ehrgeiz ist, in zehn Sätzen zu sagen, was jeder Andere in einem Buche sagt, was jeder Andere in einem Buche nicht sagt...". Implicitity, being a powerful means of text compression, leads to a significant reduction in its volume, which corresponds to the main feature of the aphorism style - information density.

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Phonetically Inflected Words and Connotative Meaning

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Abstract: *The connotative meanings of phonetically altered words in English and Uzbek languages are investigated comparatively in the article.*

Keywords: *phonostylistics, phonopragmatics, connotative meaning, metathesis, prosthesis, epithesis, apocope, emotional-expressive meaning.*

The meaning of demonstrative significance, or undertone, has to do with the socially gained worth of words. All in all, obvious importance makes sense of the additional significance of words that goes past the word reference definition. Inflection is a form of **morphology** (word formation process) in which a base word is altered to show grammatical meaning and category, such as tense, aspect, number, mood, or person. Typically, inflected words go through an affixation process, whereby a letter, or a number of letters, is added to the base word to show the grammatical change. For example, *sing - singing* - here, the inflexional suffix '-ing' indicates the action is ongoing. However, there are also several irregular inflections that don't follow the typical affixation process, and the base word is altered in terms of spelling, pronunciation, or remains the same. For example, *sheep - sheep*. Unlike regular inflections, which typically follow set rules, there are no rules around irregular inflections that need to be remembered.

As we referenced, the most widely recognized affectation process is appendage. Before we go any further, we should check out at a definition for that marginally frightening term.

Connotation is an importance notwithstanding the definitional meaning you track down in a word reference. Along these lines, it is generally difficult to decipher the importance of a word in view of the word's strict significance alone. For instance, when we utilize the word 'supper', there is a scope of potential undertones. Beside the word reference definition ('a feast'), there are related implications that we would guarantee as suggestive implications. Affixation is a morphological process (word formation process) whereby affixes (e.g., prefixes and suffixes) are added to base words to alter their meaning, word class, or grammatical meaning. So, affixation refers to the process of adding letters to a base word, but not all affixation is inflectional. **Inflection is unique in that it must show a change in grammatical meaning.** Let's take a look at two different words that have gone through the affixation process: one is an example of inflection, and one isn't.

1. Imaginable - **Unimaginable**
2. Eat - **Eaten**

In example 1, we can see that the prefix 'un-' has been added to the base word 'imaginable' to change its **semantic meaning** from something positive to negative.

Example 2, on the other hand, uses the suffix '-en' to show either the **perfect aspect** (e.g., *I have eaten two sandwiches today*) or the passive voice (e.g., *The sandwiches were eaten by me*), both of which are grammatical changes.

Types of inflection: Inflection can happen across several word classes, such as verbs, nouns, pronouns, and adjectives. The inflection of verbs is most common and is called **conjugation**, whereas the inflection of all other word classes is called **declension**.

Conjugation. The term conjugation refers to the inflection of verbs to show grammatical tense, aspect, mood, voice, and person. When discussing verbs, we usually start with their base form, e.g., *to sing, to run, to drive*; we then add inflections to the base to show grammatical meaning, such as when the action happened, who completed it, the complete status of the action, and more.

There are two tenses in English that can be created by inflections: the past and the present. We can create the **past tense** by adding the inflection '-ed' / '-d' to the end of the verb and the **present tense** by adding '-s'.

Today, he works from the office.

Yesterday, he worked at home.

Many linguists state that the future tense isn't a real tense in English as it cannot be represented with inflected verbs. Instead, we use the present tense with auxiliary verbs (e.g., *will*) to discuss the future.

The grammatical aspect refers to how an action/event extends over time. There are four main aspects in English; **simple, progressive, perfect, and progressive perfect**. The **simple aspect** presents facts, i.e., things that are always true. We don't inflect the verb based on aspect but instead follow the same rules of the tense. E.g., "*The baby sleeps every day.*" or "*The baby **slept** all day.*"

The **progressive aspect** lets us know the action/event is ongoing and not yet completed. For the verb inflection, we add '-ing' to the end of the main verb. E.g., "*The baby is **sleeping**.*"

The **perfect aspect** is used for actions/events that are completed. We use **past participles** (i.e., Verb 3) for the perfect aspect. The verb inflection for past participles is most commonly the suffix '-en'; However, there are many irregular verb inflections for the perfect aspect. E.g., "*I have **eaten** already this morning.*" and "*I have **written** 500 words today already.*" The **perfect progressive aspect** uses the verb inflection '-ing' on the main verb coupled with the auxiliary verbs had/have been. E.g., "*I **had been working** all day.*"

Voice. Grammatical voice shows the relationship between the subject or object in a sentence and the verb. The two grammatical voices are active (where the subject completes the action) and passive (where the object is acted upon). To show the passive voice, we inflect the main verb, again turning it into a past participle. E.g., "*The picture was **drawn** by me.*"

In the linguistics of the modern period, the internal possibilities of language as an aloa tool began to be studied in depth and comprehensively.

This resulted in new fields in linguistics. In particular, a branch of Methodism and Methodism appeared in phonetic Methodism, characterized by abundance and development. In phonetic Stylistics, my methodological features of speech sounds are mainly studied [1, 24-28]. Phonostilistics issues have been studied in English and Uzbek. It discusses the manifestation of the tactile edges of the language as a result of stylistic figures such as alliteration, assonance, anaphora, Epiphora, rhyme, rhythm, which are based on the repetition of speech sounds. Comparative study was carried out on the example of non-sister English and Uzbek. We reflect on the example of two languages in this article on connotative meanings in words with phonetic changes.

Repetition as a stylistic device is based on the nature of the oral form of speech, which is used for the purpose of expressing an exciting State. Emotional-expressive speech is characterized by shortness, logic, intensity, as well as the repetition of individual fragments of the stated thought. A stylistic

figure, the repetition is the most used figure in the language of poetic and publicistic works. In linguistics, the linguistic scientist O. Brik has made valuable remarks on sound repetition. In his opinion, sound repetition occurs mainly in consonant sounds, but later the term began to be used in poetic speech in reference to vowel and consonant sounds. The repetition was shown to be not only to consonant sounds, but also to others of the elements of the language structure, including word repetition, morphological parts repetition, syntactic whole repetition. The repetition stylistic tool is used to attract the attention of the listener. In it, mainly phonetic repetition performs a methodological task. The following poetic passage is written based on a sound repeat, in which we see that it mainly attracts the attention of the listener.

And his eyes have all the seeming of a demon that is dreaming.
And the lamp light over him streaming, throws his shadow on the floor;
And my soul from out this shadow that lies flat on the floor
Shall be lifted-never more. (R.Jacobson)

In the poetic stanza above, we see that a repeating stylistic figure is used through the consonants s, l, f. This condition is a phonostylistic tool, which ensures that the poem increases its effectiveness and is kept long in the reader's memory. The main task of the repetition is to make the speech impressive, concretize the thought and draw the listener's attention to it. Phonetic repetition language is an enrichment of stylistic resources, and the speaker tries to fill his intuition with a qualitative amount, realizing that the phrase is not suitable. This state of course creates repetition, while repetition enhances meaning, serving for intensity and emotionality [4,11]. Enhance the impressiveness of poetic works, from the stylistic figures of poets repetition, one can find such types of figures as alliteration, assonance, anaphora, Epiphora, misra and band (line) repetition.

Sokinu savlamli, soyabon sada ("Chollar" poem)
Salqin, silliq, so,,lim bahor ertasi ("Yashil yaproqlar")
Sim- sim yomgir, sirli so"z misol pichirlydi ona-tabiati.
Saxiyiligi optganday qat-qat
Go,,yo deydi ol, ol, olib qol (Yoz yomg,,iri)

Repetition and its features of syntactic Stylistics L in linguistics. M. Astafeva, M.H. It was studied by the Azimovs in a holistic monographic way. In their scientific work, the syntactic stylistic features of repetition are revealed on the basis of evidential examples. According to scientists, the repeat language is a source of enrichment of stylistic resources [2,14-16].

A. Mamajonov also reflected on the repetition, stating with evidential examples that it contains phonetic repetition, morphological repetition, syntactic repetition manifestations, and that such repetitions are very rarely used in the language of folk oral fiction materials, artistic and publicistic works [3,18-24]. In general linguistics at stylistic means such as alliteration, assonance, anaphora, Epiphora are recognized as different manifestations of artistic repetition.

Anaphora. Parallel structured speech fragments are a stylistic figure consisting of a repetition of an element at the beginning. This stylistic figure is used to create speech forms, which are spoken with emotion, uplifting spirit.

In English:

For want of a nail, the shoe was lost
For want of a shoe, the horse was lost,

For want of a horse, the rider was lost

For want of a rider, the battle was lost.

In Uzbek:

Qani qizlar, qani o,,rtoqlap?

Qani ko,,klam, qani go,,zal yor?

qani gullap, Qani bulbullar?

Built on a repeating basis, the anaphoras in the two languages mentioned above serve as a phonostilistic medium that evokes various emoticons in the reader and listener.

Epiphora. In poetic works, you can say that at the end of the two verses, the repetition of certain vowel or consonant sounds in the maxad of strengthening expressiveness, increasing expressiveness is called Epiphora. In other words, the repetitions that come at the end of the sentence are the Epiphora.

Un English:

When I go to the bank,

I get rattled,

The clerk rattle me,

The wickets rattle me.

The sight of money rattles me,

Everything rattles me (S.Leacock).

In Uzbek:

Uyda, oilada, dalada, qirda,

Oppoq paxta bitgan serunum yerda.

Ozod mehnat zo,,r jadal bilan

Insonni insonni qaytadan ko,,kartirganda.(H.Olimjon).

Observations show that in the poetic work of poets repeat anaphora Epiphora the most common stylistic figures bulib serves to increase the effectiveness of the work of art and performs a phonostylistic task

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Some Connotative Meanings in Literary Works

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Abstract: *The article examines how connotative meanings are expressed in literary works. The material analyzed in the article shows that the reason why authors use connotation in their literary works. The connotation in literature pertains to the emotional or cultural connections that a word, phrase, or image carries, surpassing its literal definition. It represents the implied or suggested significance that extends beyond the dictionary explanation. Connotation plays a vital part in establishing the mood, tone, and ambiance of a piece of literature. It enhances the depth and intricacy of the writing, enabling readers to interpret and comprehend the text from various perspectives.*

Keywords: *emotional, cultural, depth and complexity, sense of warmth, interpretation of literary works, vivid imagery, evoke specific emotions, reflect historical contexts, symbolize, character, setting, literal meaning.*

Connotation in literature refers to the emotional or cultural associations that a word, phrase, or image carries beyond its literal meaning. It is the implied or suggested meaning of a word or phrase that goes beyond its dictionary definition.

Connotation plays a crucial role in creating the mood, tone, and atmosphere of a literary work. It adds depth and complexity to the writing, allowing readers to interpret and understand the text on multiple levels.

Authors often use connotation to evoke specific emotions or create a particular atmosphere. For example, they may choose words with positive connotations to create a sense of warmth and happiness, or words with negative connotations to evoke fear or sadness. By carefully selecting their language, authors can manipulate readers' emotions and shape their interpretation of the text.

Connotation can also be influenced by cultural, historical, or personal contexts. Certain words or phrases may carry different connotations for different readers based on their individual experiences and backgrounds. This adds another layer of richness and complexity to the interpretation of literary works.

Authors use connotation in literature for several reasons:

1. To evoke emotions: By using words with specific connotations, authors can elicit emotional responses from their readers. This allows them to create a desired mood or atmosphere in their writing. For example, using words with positive connotations can make readers feel happy or hopeful, while words with negative connotations can evoke fear or sadness. For example:

In William Shakespeare's play "Romeo and Juliet", the word "**love**" carries *positive connotations of passion, romance, and happiness*. This evokes emotions of joy and excitement in readers as they witness the intense love between the two main characters.

In F. Scott Fitzgerald's novel "The Great Gatsby", the **color green** is often associated with *envy and wealth*. This connotation evokes emotions of longing and desire as readers witness the characters' pursuit of material success and their dissatisfaction with their current circumstances.

In Maya Angelou's poem "Still I Rise," the word "**rise**" carries *connotations of strength, resilience, and empowerment*. This evokes emotions of determination and inspiration as readers connect with the speaker's refusal to be defeated by adversity.

In George Orwell's novel 1984, the word "**Big Brother**" has *negative connotations of surveillance, control, and oppression*. This evokes emotions of fear and paranoia as readers experience the oppressive regime depicted in the story.

In Harper Lee's novel "To Kill a Mockingbird", the word "**justice**" carries *connotations of fairness, equality, and righteousness*. This evokes emotions of hope and righteousness as readers witness the characters' fight for justice in a racially divided society.

These examples demonstrate how authors use connotation to elicit specific emotions from readers and enhance the overall impact of their literary works.

2. To add depth and complexity: Connotation adds layers of meaning to a text, allowing readers to interpret the writing on multiple levels. By using words with nuanced connotations, authors can convey subtle emotions, ideas, or themes that may not be explicitly stated in the text. For example,

In Joseph Conrad's novel "Heart of Darkness", the word "**darkness**" carries *connotations of evil, mystery, and the unknown*. However, it also adds depth and complexity by symbolizing the darkness within human nature and the moral ambiguity of colonialism.

In Toni Morrison's novel "Beloved", the word "**beloved**" carries *connotations of love, affection, and endearment*. However, it adds depth and complexity by representing the haunting presence of the past, the trauma of slavery, and the complexities of motherhood.

In Virginia Woolf's novel "Mrs. Dalloway", the word "**time**" carries *connotations of passing, fleeting moments*. However, it adds depth and complexity by exploring the fluidity of time and its effect on memory, identity, and perception.

In Ernest Hemingway's novel "The Old Man and the Sea", the word "**sea**" carries *connotations of vastness, freedom, and adventure*. However, it adds depth and complexity by symbolizing life's challenges, solitude, and the relentless struggle between man and nature.

In Sylvia Plath's poem "Mirror," the word "**mirror**" carries *connotations of reflection, self-awareness, and truth*. However, it adds depth and complexity by exploring themes of aging, identity, and the inner turmoil of the speaker.

These examples showcase how authors use connotation to add layers of meaning, symbolism, and complexity to their literary works, inviting readers to delve deeper into the text and contemplate its various interpretations.

3. To shape readers' interpretation: Authors can manipulate readers' understanding and interpretation of a text by carefully selecting their language and using connotation. By choosing words with specific connotations, authors can guide readers towards a particular viewpoint or interpretation of the events or themes in the story. For example,

In F. Scott Fitzgerald's novel "The Great Gatsby", the word "**green light**" carries *connotations of hope, ambition, and the American Dream*. However, it also adds depth and complexity by symbolizing unattainable desires, the corrupting influence of wealth, and the illusory nature of the American Dream.

In William Shakespeare's play "Romeo and Juliet", the word "**star-crossed**" carries *connotations of fate, tragedy, and doomed love*. However, it shapes readers' interpretation by foreshadowing the tragic outcome of the lovers' relationship and emphasizing the external forces that conspire against them.

In George Orwell's novel "1984", the word "**Big Brother**" carries *connotations of surveillance, control, and oppression*. It shapes readers' interpretation by representing the totalitarian regime's constant monitoring of its citizens and the loss of individual freedom in a dystopian society.

In Harper Lee's novel "To Kill a Mockingbird", the word "**mockingbird**" carries *connotations of innocence, purity, and harmlessness*. It shapes readers' interpretation by symbolizing the unjust persecution of innocent individuals, such as Tom Robinson and Boo Radley, and highlighting the moral lessons of empathy and compassion.

In Emily Dickinson's poem "Hope is the Thing with Feathers," the word "**hope**" carries *connotations of resilience, optimism, and endurance*. It shapes readers' interpretation by personifying hope as a bird that sings in difficult times, offering solace and strength amidst adversity.

These examples demonstrate how connotation in literature can shape readers' understanding and interpretation of themes, symbols, and motifs, allowing for a richer and more nuanced reading experience.

4. To reflect cultural or historical contexts: Connotation can be influenced by cultural or historical contexts, and authors may use this to their advantage. By using words or phrases with connotations that resonate with a specific culture or time period, authors can create a more authentic and immersive reading experience for their audience. For example,

In Langston Hughes' poem "Harlem," the word "**dream**" carries *connotations of hope, aspirations, and the unfulfilled promises of the American Dream for African Americans during the Harlem Renaissance*. It reflects the cultural and historical context of racial inequality and the struggle for civil rights.

In Chinua Achebe's novel "Things Fall Apart", the word "**colonialism**" carries *connotations of exploitation, cultural imperialism, and the erosion of traditional African values*. It reflects the cultural and historical context of European colonization in Africa and the impact it had on indigenous cultures.

In Toni Morrison's novel "Beloved", the word "**rememory**" carries *connotations of trauma, memory, and the lasting effects of slavery on African Americans*. It reflects the cultural and historical context of the transatlantic slave trade and the ongoing legacy of slavery in America.

In Gabriel Garcia Marquez's novel "One Hundred Years of Solitude", the word "**macondo**" carries *connotations of isolation, enchantment, and the cyclical nature of history*. It reflects the cultural and historical context of Latin American colonialism, political instability, and the blending of reality and myth in magical realism.

In John Steinbeck's novel "The Grapes of Wrath", the word "**Okies**" carries *connotations of poverty, displacement, and resilience*. It reflects the cultural and historical context of the Great Depression and the Dust Bowl migration, highlighting the struggles faced by migrant workers during that time.

These examples demonstrate how connotation in literature can reflect and convey the cultural and historical contexts in which they were written, providing insight into social issues, power dynamics, and collective experiences.

5. To create vivid imagery: Connotation can help authors paint vivid pictures in the minds of their readers. By using words with rich connotations, authors can create detailed and evocative descriptions that bring their settings, characters, and events to life. For example,

In Emily Dickinson's poem "A narrow Fellow in the Grass," the phrase "**narrow fellow**" is a *connotation for a snake, creating a vivid image of a slithering creature hidden in the grass.*

In F. Scott Fitzgerald's novel "The Great Gatsby", the phrase "**valley of ashes**" is a *connotation for a desolate, industrial wasteland, creating a vivid image of a bleak and polluted landscape.*

In William Shakespeare's play "Romeo and Juliet", the phrase "**Juliet is the sun**" is a *connotation for beauty and radiance, creating a vivid image of Juliet's captivating presence.*

In Edgar Allan Poe's poem "The Raven," the word "**nevermore**" is a *connotation for despair and hopelessness, creating a vivid image of an ominous raven repeatedly uttering this word.*

In J.R.R. Tolkien's novel "The Hobbit", the phrase "**Misty Mountains**" is a *connotation for mystery and grandeur, creating a vivid image of towering peaks shrouded in mist.*

These examples show how connotation in literature can evoke strong visual imagery, allowing readers to vividly imagine the settings, characters, and emotions described in the text.

Overall, connotation in literature helps authors convey deeper meanings and create a more vivid and engaging reading experience for the audience. authors use connotation in literature to enhance their writing, evoke emotions, add depth and complexity, shape readers' interpretation, reflect cultural or historical contexts, and create vivid imagery. It is a powerful tool that allows authors to engage and connect with their audience on a deeper level.

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Theoretican and Practical Investigation of the Terms of Etics of the XVI-XVII Centuries

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Abstract: *The article deals with issues of formation and development of the terms of ethics in the XVI-XVII centuries in the English language and different points of language specialists on this field which is considered to be very actual for investigation. The views and scientific theories given in this article serve as a basic source when highlighting various aspects of the terms of ethics of the Renaissance period.*

Keywords: *principle, science, language, ratio, vocabulary, lexicography, lexical meaning, semantics, feature, linguists, research, stages, phonetics, morphology, term, structure, ethics, society, diachronic, phonology, morphology, syntax, terminological system, philosophy, lexical system, semantic-syntactical parameters, word combination, prepositions, parts of speech.*

Introduction. In the historical development of the English language, the Era we are examining is especially important, since this period the existence of the linguistic norm becomes undoubted. The steady development of production and social consciousness in the Middle Ages, certain achievements of science and technology led to the fact that the cultivated ideological postulates began to restrain the further progress of mankind. Providing the relative freedom of the human person, and hence a certain flourishing of his creative activity, feudalism could not, however, create the necessary conditions for the all-round connections of the individual with nature and society and, thereby, the material prerequisites for the all-round development of man. It took “a kind of reorientation towards the restoration of the bodily material ideal of being of antiquity, accompanied by a gradual rejection of the ascetic-quietist ideals of the Middle Ages, which is reflected in the self-designation of the coming early bourgeois era - the Renaissance”. This was also facilitated by a number of crisis discoveries in natural science, which radically changed the picture of the world. Thanks to the great discoveries of N.Copernicus, G. Bruno, G. Galileo and others, new experimental natural science appears, new branches of science are rapidly developing¹. Under the influence of great geographical and scientific discoveries, religious and mythical ideas about the world collapse and the principles of a scientific- realistic worldview are gradually formed, which, accordingly, leads to changes in ethical and aesthetic canons. As a result, the results become unexpected, impudent - assumptions and guesses, which naturally leads to an urgent need for a critical analysis of the knowledge gained. The formation of a new worldview was given impetus by the great socio-economic and technical shifts associated with the names of J. Hilbert, T. Garriot, D. Napier, W. Garvey and others. The new powerful rise of realism in literature is associated with the formation of bourgeois nations and the national self-consciousness of the English people, which is expressed in a specific national culture and becomes generally accessible and democratic in nature. Already Shakespeare’s dramaturgy “acquires the character of a clearly expressed national certainty in the living reproduction of historical processes and topical social

¹ Методологический анализ историко-философского знания. – Киев: Выша школа, 1984. – С. 157.

conflicts, remaining renaissance in terms of the breadth of human life and the height of the sound of humanistic ideals”². The completion of this process was undoubtedly facilitated by a comprehensive study of the classical heritage, which led primarily to the enrichment of the vocabulary of the English language. Scientific works are already being created in English, translated literature is undergoing significant development, the scientific and philosophical movement is widely deployed, the crown of which is the materialistic philosophical system of Francis Bacon - the founder of all experimental science and which completes the philosophy of the Renaissance and opens a new stage in the development of European scientific philosophical thought of the New Time.

Main part. The establishment of the English language as the language of scientific and philosophical literature took a more difficult path. There were no significant changes in the language of science of this period, since “Latin in the linguistic life of England in the XVI-XVII centuries and even the XVIII century was the center around which the search for the norm of the English literary language was conducted. However, in 1531 Thomas Eliot wrote the book “The Governor” / in English. This was the first attempt to create a scholarly work in the native - English - language. T. Eliot made it quite deliberately in order to prove that serious works can be written in English, although the English language of that time did not yet have its own specialized industry terminology³. Formation of ethical and philosophical vocabulary in the XVI-XVII centuries in England took place, on the one hand, under the influence of the national specifics of socio-economic and cultural development, and on the other, it reflected the main trends of general linguistic evolution. Despite the presence of two contradictory and opposite directions - purism, on the one hand, and the widespread use of Latinisms to create missing terms, on the other. Both the first and second directions are indicated by the conscious nature of the struggle for a particular language policy. A new interest in language issues was relevant not only for England, it was a sign of the times when the struggle for the native language is becoming one of the most effective ways of manifesting national identity. Many researchers note that the main factor of scientific thinking in this era is the interpreter’s ideological criteria, depending on which the research methodology is built. This also fully explains the scientific orientation of the formation of scientific terminology. Therefore, in the terminology of ethical and philosophical content, there may be lexical units that, at first glance, refer to the terminology of natural and didactic psychological sciences. However, the phenomena related to them are included in the scope of the author’s philosophical worldview, therefore the meanings of these units also have a philosophical character. In England of the XVI-XVII centuries, supporters of the universal use of the language (Thomas Nash, George Puttenham, Edmund Spenser, Thomas Eliot, etc.) sharply raised the question of replenishing its vocabulary and, above all, creating an English scientific terminology. A review of the genre diverse literature of this period shows that the bulk of terminological vocabulary is created by rethinking the semantics of words and phrases of the general literary language. Moreover, its characteristic feature is imagery and connotation, that is, an expansive interpretation of a word- concept. This imagery is characteristic of the initial stage of term creation - when a new concept is introduced for the national linguistic consciousness and which is figuratively compared with already known concepts for clarity. It is with this phenomenon that we are faced when we analyze the terminology⁴ that reflects the worldview of a particular writer or thinker. This is especially clearly

² Шадманов К.Б. Английская духовность и язык. – Бухара, 2010. – С. 164.

³ Ступин Л.П. Проблема нормативности в истории английской лексикографии XVI-XX вв. – Л.: ЛГУ, 1989. – С. 42.

⁴ Askarovna, S. M., & Djurabayevna, D. N. (2019). Some principles of the formation and development of ethical terms in the English language in the XVI-XVIII centuries. *International Journal on Integrated Education*, 2(6), 31-39; Shukurova, M. A. (2017). Coherence and cohesion as essential parts in effective writing. *Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука*, (1 (1)), 143-145; Шукурова, М. А. (2021). Анализ специальной лексики английского языка

manifested in works of a deep, vivid philosophical and ethical orientation, where the author strives for the most objective, in his opinion, reflection of the phenomena of the social reality of his era. The actual linguistic picture in England was quite complex both in territorial and socio-political terms. Although the existence of Latin in the higher spheres of communication of the English language was still largely supported by the strength of centuries-old traditions, in the 16th century the activity of humanists and their views on the relationship between the two languages became a new impetus. In the field of the structure of the language, the main questions concerned spelling and expansion of the lexical composition. Learning the native language in England is gradually becoming an end in itself. At the end of the 16th century, work began on the description of the language and its codification. This work includes grammarians and orthoepists, first of all (Hart, William Bullokar, A. Gill, C. Butler, C. Cooper). Simultaneously with them, lexicographers also developed their activities, striving to fix the vocabulary of the language. If the first such dictionaries were bilingual Latin-English dictionaries of new words, then at the beginning of the 16th century dictionaries of so-called "difficult" words appeared (Robert Cowdrey, H. Cockeram, E. Coles). Bilingual dictionaries reached their apogee in the 16th century. These are the dictionaries of Thomas Eliot, Richard Huloet, Thomas Cooper, John Barrett, John Ryder, etc. All this leads to the fact that the character and position of the original and translated literature is changing: it becomes highly demanded. The conquest of the English language the right to use in all genres of scientific and literary creativity was the most important issue of the time. At the same time, the interaction of the scientific and artistic literary language with the spoken language should be emphasized, for the language in which Shakespeare spoke was the language in which he wrote. Based on the foregoing, it can be argued that the tasks of the language here went far beyond pure linguistics - it was a struggle for a new humanistic thinking, for a genuine cultural flourishing, which required adequate forms of its linguistic explication, expressed in a vivid form also in the process of term creation in the field of philosophical vocabulary in general and vocabulary of ethics in particular. The creation of scientific terminology on a national-English basis by significantly filling the lexicon was on the agenda.

In the works of most domestic and foreign linguists of recent decades, it is noteworthy that the development of terminology in them is associated with the reflection not only of the scientific and technical, but also the social, linguocultural and culturological aspects of the development of society. However, the socio-linguistic aspect of the evolution of terminological vocabulary is still did not receive wide coverage, such as structural-semantic, morphological, syntactic, stylistic and other characteristics of the formation and functioning of units of a terminological nature. True, in the domestic science of recent years, works have appeared that seriously and in detail consider this aspect from the standpoint of the philosophy of language. This gap, apparently, is due to the fact that most of the works are aimed at studying specific technical terminological systems, which are studied mainly within the framework of one language and are sufficiently distinguishable from general literary vocabulary. Meanwhile, since terminology is emerging and developing within the framework of the national language system, it must be organically linked with the vocabulary of the general literary language. If the first publications in the field of terminology focused researchers, first of all, on the issues of streamlining technical terminology, today terminology has grown into an independent branch of linguistics, which faces a variety of practical tasks: from teaching languages and lexicographic systematization, automatic translation and information retrieval, to problems rationing and deep structures of terminology as the most mobile and receptive part of the lexicon of the national language.

XVI века по аспектам терминологичности. *МЕЖДУНАРОДНЫЙ ЖУРНАЛ ИСКУССТВО СЛОВА*, 4(2); Askarovna, S. M. (2021, March). Comparative investigation on the semantic meaning of some terms of ethics of the XVI-XVII centuries. In *E-Conference Globe* (pp. 285-287).

As a result, fundamental research has appeared that gives an overview of the state and prospects for the development of terminology, highlighting the main theoretical and methodological issues related to the ordering, standardization and unification of terminology, with the development of dictionaries in the context of bilingualism and multilingualism. The attention of many is also attracted by the history of the development of terminological systems in connection with the history or other branch of knowledge. To a lesser extent, the problems associated with lexical-comparative, typological studies in the terminological field have been developed. Actual directions of linguistic study of complex theoretical issues of the creation and development of terminology in national languages, the principles of the formation of terminology systems and problems associated with the improvement of terms and their spelling, requiring attention from both specialists in various fields of knowledge and linguists, are reflected in the collective monographic works of the latter years. The terminology of the humanities was much less often the subject of fundamental monographic and dissertation research. Meanwhile, it is the humanitarian, especially the ethical and philosophical terminology that allows us to trace how the vocabulary of the general literary language is transformed into the language of science. Therefore, the study of the humanitarian and, in particular, the terminology of ethics seems to be very relevant, since this layer of special vocabulary is the most developed, rich and saturated language of the scientific worldview. Optimally accurate sampling of data on a certain slice of language development allows the method of synchronous analysis. However, in order to establish some general trends, it becomes necessary to trace those changes that are determined by the time factor. This applies primarily to the semantic area, and, as M.A. Halliday, the line between intra-linguistic changes and socially determined ones is rather vague. It is appropriate to recall this remark in connection with the analysis of the vocabulary of ethics, which is especially socially susceptible and ideologically vulnerable. The essence of linguistic changes is well defined by M. Samuels in his work "Linguistic Evolution". All changes occur according to the laws of linguistic development⁵ and, therefore, are in principle distinguishable, although some have decisive meanings, while others do not. It should be noted that changes in the semantic nature are not necessarily accompanied by transformations of the formal structure of linguistic units (affixation, word composition, etc.). This pattern is of great importance for linguistic research when comparing structural changes in form and content in order to establish the source of transformations. The reasons for such changes are manifold. For example, S. Ulmann indicates four main ones: 1) linguistic and 2) historical, including: a) change of objects; b) change of public institutions; c) change of ideas; d) changing scientific concepts; 3) social and 4) psychological, including: a) emotional; b) the impact of taboo. According to the methodology of modern linguistics, this scheme must be somewhat rebuilt, highlighting the historical factors reflecting the essence and basic laws of social development. Then - the social factors in which these laws get concrete implementation. In third place are psychological factors that fix the results of the operation of the laws of social development in a specific area, in particular, in the process of communication. And, finally, the fourth stage is the concrete linguistic realization of all the above-mentioned patterns. All this fully applies to terminological vocabulary. So, for example, the development and spread of the

⁵ Shukurova, M. A. (2017). Useful strategies in teaching grammar in english language classes. *Міжнародний науковий журнал Інтернаука*, (1 (1)), 146-148; Askarovna, S. M. (2021). Historical background on the systematization of the vocabulary of ethics. *ACADEMICIA: An International Multidisciplinary Research Journal*, 11(3), 25-29; Шукурова, М. А. XVI-XVIII АСРЛАРДА ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДА ЭТИКА АТАМАЛАРИНИНГ РИВОЖЛАНИШИГА ДОИР БАЪЗИ МАСАЛАЛАР НЕКОТОРЫЕ ВОПРОСЫ РАЗВИТИЯ ЭТИЧЕСКИХ ТЕРМИНОВ В АНГЛИЙСКОМ ЯЗЫКЕ XVI-XVIII ВЕКОВ SOME ISSUES ON THE DEVELOPMENT OF TERMS OF ETHICS IN THE. *ANIQ VA TAVIIY FANLAR*, 165; Шукурова-БухГУ, М. А. (2020). КОРРЕЛЯЦИЯ СОЗНАНИЯ, ЯЗЫКА И СТИЛЯ НАУЧНО-ФИЛОСОФСКОГО ИЗЛОЖЕНИЯ ПЕРИОДА XVI-XVII ВЕКОВ. *ТАЪЛИМ ТИЗИМИДА ЧЕТ ТИЛЛАРНИ ФРГАНИШНИНГ ЗАМОНАВИЙ МУАММОЛАРИ ВА ИСТИҚБОЛЛАРИ* *Халқаро илмий-амалий анжуман 5-6 март 2020 йил*, 597.

English language in the XV-XVII centuries to those areas of scientific and philosophical literature in which Latin previously dominated, - notes V.N. Yartseva, - posed with all its acuteness the problem of terminology and, in general, the problem of replenishing the vocabulary of the English language. 100 It is obvious that V.V. Nalimov, T. Savory, D. Davie and others mean a structurally stable and, indeed, in many cases isomorphic chemical, medical and other nomenclature. The latter, however, is not an element of the terminological system, since, not being literary and normative, the nomenclature does not mean, but “labels” scientific concepts⁶. In addition, it should also be noted that the nomenclature is a derivative of the “third” order of terms, acquiring a stable, often abbreviated form, and is not numerous or, at least, a significant layer in the general mass of terminological vocabulary. As for the immediate sphere of philosophical, including ethical, vocabulary, in most works on terminology, the authors define the term based on the specifics of the studied terminology. There are many such definitions, but none of them fits the definition of a philosophical term. Since the development of the terminological system is determined by the specifics of the field of human activity, the philosophical terminological system is determined, first of all, by the system of concepts and ideas of a particular philosophical school, trend, or even an individual author. Based on the foregoing, we define the term ethics as a unit of vocabulary included as an integral component in one or another thematic group of a certain philosophical and terminological system, and quite clearly denoting a certain concept within this philosophical and ethical system. At the same time, in the study and description of terminological units, where the influence of the semantic factor is especially noticeable, the main attention should be paid to the meaningful characteristics of the terms, and not to their morphological or morphosyntactic structure, since this concerns the philosophical terminology of ethics and morality.

Conclusion. A term is a reflection of an abstract concept by means of language. The concepts associated with a given area of knowledge constitute a system of concepts, and the words denoting them constitute a system of terms. Terminology presents the greatest difficulty in ordering special words. At the same time, terminology is the most important part of special vocabulary, it is she who “actively participates in the production, accumulation, synthesis and socialization of knowledge about the essence of things, phenomena, processes in nature, society and thinking”. The terminology of a given area of knowledge is a set of terms accepted in it. Terminological system - all terms of a certain field of knowledge, taken in their relationship. The structure of a terminological system is the nature of the relationship of its constituent terms, or, in other words, what kind of semantic relations exist between the terms of a given system and which of them (that is, of these relations) prevail in it.

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The Relationship between Man and Nature in the Works of the American Writer Mary Alice Monro

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Abstract: *This research work is one of the first scientific studies devoted to the study of the characteristics of eco-fiction in the work of the American writer Mary Alice Monroe. Its relevance serves to introduce the genre to Uzbek-speaking and other worldwide readers and expand the scope of research in this field. Due to the works of complex and dramatic nature, which acquired a special essence in American literature in the 19th-20th centuries, theoretical literary scholars such as Henry David Thoreau, Ralph Waldo Emerson, John Moore, Aldo Leopold, Rachel Carson made a great contribution to the philosophical formation of the concept of nature in American literature, and their works mainly focused on the image of nature, environmental problems, and human nature, devoted to its philosophical relationship with the universe.*

Keywords: *eco-fiction, literary theme, characters, setting, eco-motives.*

INTRODUCTION

This research work is one of the first scientific studies devoted to the study of the characteristics of eco-fiction in the work of the American writer Mary Alice Monroe. Its relevance serves to introduce the genre to Uzbek-speaking and other worldwide readers and expand the scope of research in this field. Due to the works of complex and dramatic nature, which acquired a special essence in American literature in the 19th-20th centuries, theoretical literary scholars such as Henry David Thoreau, Ralph Waldo Emerson, John Moore, Aldo Leopold, Rachel Carson made a great contribution to the philosophical formation of the concept of nature in American literature, and their works mainly focused on the image of nature, environmental problems, and human nature, devoted to its philosophical relationship with the universe.

By the 21st century, the problem of ecology has become the most urgent for the whole world. Environmental problems such as animal population, air quality, water quality, and global climate change are reflected in the novels of contemporary American literature, especially in Rachel Carson's "Silent Spring", James Graham Ballard's "The Drought", Ursula Le Guin's "The Dispossessed," and in "Carbon Dreams" by Susan M.Gaines and "Solar" by Ian McEwan.

As a result of the environmental movements led by women, in the 90s of the 20th century, novels created by women writers expressing their sympathies through both feminism and environmental themes began to appear in the world, enriching American literature and this new type of criticism against the dominant system in American culture was founded by ecofeminists. Eco-feminist writers including Joan Lynn Slonczewski, Ursula K. Le Guin, Miriam Simos Starhawk, Sherry S. Tepper, , Suzy McKee Charnas, Suzette Haden Elgin, Octavia Butler, Barbara Kingsolver, Margaret Atwood, Sally Miller Gearhart, Dorothy Bryant, Marge Percy, Marian Engel and Alice Walker, opposed gender discrimination and criticized androcentrism and anthropocentrism. They created works imbued

with the feelings of preserving the environment, sympathy for the fate of the Mother Earth, always being in harmony with nature, and left their names forever sealed in world literature.

The famous writer Mary Alice Monroe, who entered the modern American literature with her novels that uniquely describe the relationship between man and nature, showed herself in a series of novels of the eco-fiction genre with a style that combined her deep sympathy for people and a naturalistic worldview. M.E. Monroe's books on environmental topics make him known as a bestselling novelist. As a result of Monroe's family's move to the Isle of Palms, a major event occurred in the writer's evolutionary development. Her writing began to combine feminist themes with environmental messages and metaphors, thus bridging her life as a writer and conservationist.

Mother Nature is the main theme of M.A. Monroe's "*Beach House Series*" and the novels "*Time is a River*", "*Sweetgrass*", "*The Butterfly's Daughter*", "*Skyward*", although the author describes this theme as a family that we experience in everyday life, it was analyzed that it was able to illuminate in communion with the complex but sacred feelings related to the environment.

METHODOLOGY OF THE RESEARCH

The notion of an eco-fiction and its principles are studied in many prominent books and manuals related to the theory of literature such as in Patrick D. Murphy's *Further Afield in the Study of Nature-Oriented Literature*. (2000), Jim. Dwyer's "This Way to Sustainability Conference", *Mary Woodbury's "Dragonfly Eco-fiction Database"*(2014), Mike Vasey's "Bioregional Studies" Correspondence with Jim Dwyer. (1996), R.Nesh's "Dikaya priroda i amerikanskiy razum"(Wildlife and American Mind) (2004), John Stadler's "Eco-fiction"(1978), Carolyn Merchant's "In Radical ecology: the search for a livable world" (1992), Charlene Spretnak's "Ecofeminism: Our Roots and Flowering. Reweaving the World: The Emergence of Feminism, edited by Irene Diamond and Gloria Ornstein (1990). The theme of eco-feminism was also specially studied in the works of Russian literary scientists such as E.R. Martynova, E.S. Burmistrova and S.V. Grechishkina.

Research methods. The method employed in this research is descriptive, semantic-interpretation and stylistic analysis which aimed at identifying principles of eco-fiction genre.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

M.E. Monroe was able to skillfully interpret global ecological ideas and the fact that nature protection is a topical issue through his many works. As a result of this research, it is necessary to highlight several unique artistic elements of the author's works related to the eco-fiction genre:

- Eco-epigraphs
- Aphorisms
- Scientific facts
- Organization names
- Personal diary
- Current pictures
- Environmental calls (point of view, sound)

1. We can find meaningful words of H.D. Thoreau, a naturalistic writer, about nature in Monroe's novel "Time is a River". One of the chapters in this work of the writer, who is used to starting the chapters of his works mainly with **epigraphs** and scientific facts, begins with the following thoughts of Thoreau:

"I went to the woods because I wished to live deliberately, to face only the essential facts of life and see if I could not learn what it had to teach, and not, when I came to die, discover that I had not lived"

In this passage, it is mentioned that it is possible to learn what the meaning of life should be while living in the mountains, and then it is necessary not to regret that it was not enough to live.

In another chapter of the work, there is another wise word: "*Time is the substance from which I am made. Time is a river which carries me along. But I am the river.*" The above words of J.L. Borges can be clearly understood through the proverb "Time erodes a mountain, water gnaws a rock." Time, like a river, flows only forward. It cannot be stopped or reversed.

2. In the novel "Beach House for Rent", Monroe tries to emphasize that the events experienced by the heroes of the work are directly related to the lifestyle of these birds, their nature and their conservation, by presenting **actual pictures** of rare birds in each section. The author reveals one of the features of the eco-fiction genre through the presence of color pictures of birds that are declining on the coast of America, such as Red knot, American Oyster, Semipalmated Sandpiper, and Brown Pelican, taken by skilled photographers. Also, the appearance of Heather, one of the protagonists of the work, is described as beautiful and graceful as the birds in the work. ("She's very waiflike....Tinyboned and slender.....She's rather like her canaries"¹).

3. In all the eco-fiction works of M.Monro, any animal or animal takes part, of course, **scientific facts** are given at the beginning about the way of life, species and characteristics of that representative of nature, as well as, if we talk about a place, interesting specific information about the landscape, flora and fauna of this place.

*Hatchlings are two inches long when they emerge from the nest. Adults weigh in at 250-400 pounds and the shell length can measure more than three feet in length. It takes 20-30 years for them to mature and reproduce but no one knows for certain how long they live. It could be as long as 100 years.*²

Providing such information serves to ensure the scientific and genre complexity of the work. There is no doubt that the balance of both scientific and literary texts in one work will help the reader to improve his ecological and geographical knowledge and spirituality.

4. The presence of **the names of organizations** involved in environmental protection in all works of the writer calling for the preservation of nature helps to form ecological culture while reading the work. In addition, during the writing of each work, Monroe spent a long time in these organizations and became familiar with their activities and contribution to nature. Monroe is still active as a conservationist. Among other things, Monroe serves on the South Carolina Aquarium Board and is a member of The Leatherback Trust, a non-profit sea turtle conservation organization. is coming He is especially proud of his 20 years as an official volunteer with the Island Turtle Team, the group that first sparked his love of sea turtles and is the inspiration for his Beach House series saga. The names of the following environmental organizations can be found in Monroe's environmental works:

Island Turtle Team, South Carolina Aquarium, Sea Turtle Hospital, South Carolina Center for Birds of Prey, South Carolina Department of Natural Resources, La Cruz Habitat Protection, the Coastal Conservation League, The National Trust for Historic Preservation, Friends of Coastal South Carolina, Ducks Unlimited, Surfrider International, Charleston Waterkeeper and etc.

In the prefaces to "Beach House", "Swimming Lessons", "Sweetgrass", and "Skyward", M..A.Monroe expresses his gratitude to organizations and passionate workers who are willing to teach people about the preservation of nature and its unique secrets. At the end of the works, he gives personal appeals to the readers urging them to contribute to the protection of ecology, environment and wild nature. Along

¹ Monroe M.A. Beach House for Rent.—New York: Gallery books, 2017.—p.303

² Monroe M.A. An Ocean Boulevard.—New York: Gallery books, 2020.—p.152

with being influenced by the textile events during the work, giving the names of such real environmental organizations encourages the characters in the work to feel as if they are standing next to us.

CONCLUSION

It is the need of the hour for a mature person of the new century to be able to show the elements of ecological culture. Ecological culture is a high indicator of practical activity aimed at acquiring a deep knowledge of the environment, a sense of nature protection, caring for plants and animals, rational use of natural resources, concern for their reproduction. A person who can reflect these qualities can be called the owner of ecological culture.

In Monroe's novel "Skyward", the character of Roy Simmons, who is far from ecological culture, always hunts birds of prey to bring food to his family. At a time when eagles, hawks, falcons and other game birds are included in the Red Book, this hero's act is a sign of neglect of nature. His son, Brady, takes responsibility for his father's deed and is sent to a care center for injured and distressed birds of prey as moral punishment. During the play, while serving his sentence at the bird treatment center, Brady has to take care of an eagle shot by his father, and the love of the staff causes Brady to take a positive turn and increase his environmental culture. If we pay attention to the address at the end of the book, we are once again convinced that Monroe is not only an artist, but also an environmental conservationist:

*"How many of us have looked into a brilliant sky and felt our emotions stir at the sight of a hawk, falcon or eagle riding a thermal? Yet few of us know much about them.....Human interference through loss of habitat, toxins and trauma is by far the greatest cause of their death."*³ The author calls the reader to environmental awareness so that all birds of prey can live safely, like the image of birds in need of care mentioned in the work.

In the current era of globalization, the problem of ecology has become the most urgent for the whole world - scientific and technical progress, although it changes human life for the better, does not pass without harmful consequences for nature and does not affect human health. Such problems are reflected in the contemporary literature of the United States, which can be seen in the environmental features of Mary Alice Monroe's works.

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THE CONTRIBUTION OF EASTERN ALLOMS IN THE FORMATION OF THE MAQAMLAR VEIL SYSTEM.

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Annotation: This article talks about the contribution of Eastern scholars in the formation of the Uzbek national music art, in particular, the status curtain system. It is known that the history of national music goes back to the very distant past. Milly's music tradition is closely related to the tradition of maqam performance and continues to this day. The reason for its longevity is the great works of the great thinkers of the East, as mentioned above.

Key words: Eastern scholars, creativity, history, statuses, musical sound system, performance, tradition, national music.

The heritage of the musical culture of the Uzbek people has a very long history. In the course of historical development, performance forms close to each other in form and style, such as classical folk music, status art, folk compositional ways, as well as folklore - amateur musical heritage, have complemented each other. This musical heritage of ours is manifested even today as a part of our spiritual culture.

Today, attention to our national and spiritual values, traditions, forgotten and historically valuable traditions, and the process of their reform have become a priority. Attention to our national values, traditions, and spiritual wealth has increased to the state level. Currently, a lot of work is being done to carefully preserve and restore the spiritual wealth left by our ancestors, including musical culture, and to keep pace with the times. In this regard, our great spiritual wealth, which our ancestors left us as a legacy, serves as the main factor.

In the meeting of President Sh. Mirziyoyev with the intellectuals of our country on the topic "Development of literature and art, culture is a solid foundation for raising the spiritual world of our people": along with the development of our culture and art and positive trends in this regard, some negative situations, their social life objectively and critically evaluating the impact, actual problems waiting for their solution and their elimination. They deeply analyzed the activities of creative associations, the Ministry of Culture and the associations and organizations within it, and emphasized the importance of increasing the role and role of creative intellectuals in the life of society and the process of reforms.

The experience gained during the years of development of independence, all the historical changes and innovations that are being implemented in the construction of a great country in the future, which is recognized by the public as New Uzbekistan, the path of development suitable for us, are brought to the heart and pride of our people. has a great impact. As a result of these effects, PF-6000 of May 26, 2020 of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to further increase the role and influence of the sphere of culture and art in the life of society" In accordance with the Decree of the

Republic of Uzbekistan, the Uzbek National Music Art Institute named after Yunus Rajabi was established within the framework of the Ministry of Culture of the Republic of Uzbekistan. It is known from history that our musical culture, which is the main link of our spirituality, traditional performance, status performances and composition have always been recognized as spiritual food in the daily life of our people. The people sought salvation from music in difficult days, and songs and music accompanied them in happy days. After all, in today's blessed days, at a time when we are realizing our identity, it is natural to rely on our national musical culture, which is a part of our great spirituality, inherited from our ancestors, and to turn to our traditional songs. All this is important in the upbringing of a mature generation, in the formation of the spiritual worldview of young people.

Our traditional music and songs have always called people to faith, kindness and humanity. Even today, without losing its relevance, it remains one of the main factors in the formation of independence, the consciousness of working people, and the education of a well-rounded generation. The classic examples

created in the professional traditions of music, the tunes and songs created in the course of folk ceremonies have been living and developing over time on the basis of their own traditions.

The contribution of the great thinkers and scholars of the East in the creation of these musical and cultural heritages and passing them down to us is incomparable. Their works have been studied by many scientists for many years. Not only in our country, but also in neighboring countries and abroad, a number of scientific works, dissertations on the topic, and hundreds of scientific articles have been published in this regard. Our musical culture is recognized as a product of Eastern Islamic civilization. Because, scientists say, during the Islamic renaissance, great works were done in the fields of culture and art, as well as in all fields. In the Middle East, the theory of the musical sound system was also created by Central Asian scholars. Abu Yusuf Yaqub Al-Kindi (died 870-873), Abu Nasr Al-Farabi (873-950), Abu Ali ibn Sina (980-1037), Safiuddin al-Urmawi (1216-1294), Qutbuddin Al-Sherazi (1236 -born), Abdurrahman Jami (1414-1492) in the research conducted by such thinkers, these issues are widely covered. If we study the shashmaqom and all the maqam veils included in it in the section of the sound system, we can find the penta tonic, which is said to belong to ancient China, the Pythagorean sound system, the natural sound system, and even the sound lines of the Indian shuruti. According to the researchers, the scientific research of Eastern scientists on music is evaluated as a continuation of the work carried out by Greek scientists.

According to the sources, the Pythagoreans created a way to determine the intervals called the 2:1 octave interval from the point where the length of the string is divided by two, the fifth from the point divided by 3:2, and the quarter from the 4:3 ratio. The interest of Eastern scholars in Greek science was clearly demonstrated in the 9th century, when the "House of Wisdom" was opened in Baghdad. Ancient Greek treatises, including musical treatises, began to be translated into Arabic here.

Abu Yusuf Yaqub Al-Kindi translated Greek treatises and introduced the Arabic names of Greek musical terms. (Greek - "music", Arabic - "al-musiqi", etc.) Al-Kindi is also considered to be the first to transfer the Pythagorean ideas about musical intervals to Arabic letters and oud strings. Scientists have emphasized that the sound system created by Al-Kindi is close to the sound system created by Pythagoras along the circle of fifths. He translated Greek treatises and introduced not only the Arabic names of Greek terms (Greek. "music" - Arabic. al-musikiy, etc.), but also

Pythagoras' "perfect system" methods, the ratio of interval quantities in music being considered as the ratio of prime numbers in mathematics, Al-Kindi was the first to record musical tones and melodies in tablature form using Arabic letters and the strings of the oud. At the same time, the Greek instrument, the lyre, was replaced by the oud, which connected the "alien" teachings of the Greeks with the musical practice of Muslims. Since then, the oud has been recognized as the most "perfect" instrument in musicology. Thus, the four oud strings represent the four basic elements (water, earth, air, fire), the four directions of the winds, the seasons, the quarters of the moon, the quarters of the day, the four ages of human life, the four in the human body Rttta corresponded to "juice". (phlegm, blood, black and yellow grass) and so on. Whereas each of the seven tones corresponded to the seven planets, and the twelve signs of the zodiac corresponded to the twelve main components of the oud, which are four strings, four pegs, and four curtain (places to put fingers on the plate of the instrument).

Al-Kindi's scientific traditions were continued by two famous philosophers Abu Nasr Al-Farabi and Ibn Sina. Al-Farabi's famous big book on music was a model of scientific description of music for later authors. The merits of this scientist were one of the most unique discoveries of the theory of musical rhythms (iyqah) belonging to the noble local Muslim world, not belonging to the Greeks. At the same time, al-Farabi and Ibn Sina elaborated on the nature of musical sound (saut) and the subject of different intervals such as "jins" and "jams". Al-Farabi (873-950) scientific and cultural heritage is multifaceted, but music theory has a special place in it.

Al-Farabi's unique work called "Kitab al-musiqi al-kabir" or "The Big Book of Music" is studied with great interest abroad. The manuscript of more than a thousand pages, which was completed in the first half of the 10th century (943 AD), represents a new direction of musicology, that is, the performance culture and the uniqueness of the musical works of Muslim composers. Al-Farabi not only creatively processed the musicology works of his predecessors, but also analyzed his own observations. Through the works created by Aristotle, Plato, and Ptolemy, he deeply studied the origin of ancient Greek culture, as

well as the unique culture of nomadic peoples, the people of Sogd, Khorasan, and the powerful empires of the Sassanids and Kushans. In the historical sources, it is said that in the following centuries (XIV-XV) many more innovations were created in the development of the Eastern musical sound system. At the same time, the sound systems produced first by Greek and then by Eastern scientists were repeatedly reformed. Eastern musical sound system was based on the sounds of intervals such as bakiya - 90 cents, bakiya mujannabi - 114 cents, taniniy - 204 cents, taniny mujannabi - 180 cents in the ancient sound system enlightened by Pythagoras and Al-Kindiy. They were put into a whole, and "Ilmi-advor" was created, which is famous in the history of music. The inventor of this musical system is called Safiuddin Urmawi. This created musical-theoretical doctrine later caused other authors to write musical treatises. Abdurrahman Jami's work on music included the achievements of his predecessors - al-Farabi, Ibn Sina, Safiuddin Urmavi, Abdul Qadir Maroghi. His work "Musical Risolai" became the most famous and rare work in the world of musicology and authority. The first part of the work is devoted to the teaching of composition, the second to the teaching of rhythm and method. Maqam explores the sound system by studying total intervals and sound systems (gender, totals, and other sound systems based on the 17-step octave scale of the oud). The conclusion is that it is possible to talk about a number of other representatives of the great oriental scholars whose names were mentioned above, but this article is limited in scope. In this way, thanks to the significant contributions of thinkers, invaluable musical cultural values such as Shashmaqom, Tashkent-Fergana maqams, Khorezm maqams, folk classical musical heritage were created in the following periods. Our task today is to carefully preserve the works of the past great scholars, thinkers, master artists, the spiritual wealth they left for us, and to work diligently to leave them to the next generation. In this way, our state has created all the needs and amenities. An example of this is the opening of the Uzbek National Music Art Institute named after Yunus Rajabi in our capital and the establishment of national music art education in it. In the future, we hope that generations of scholars like our great ancestors will emerge from this university.

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CULTURAL EVENTS AND THEIR CREATIVE IMPACT ON THE MINDS OF YOUNG PEOPLE

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Annotation : In article discussion problem of influential of cultural work among the masses to youth sense and rise their affect.

Key words : culture, youth, cultural work among the masses, sense, transformation, affect, influential, creativ, actively.

The global changes and transformation processes taking place in the world today are connected with the support, creative activity, and renewal of consciousness of young people. 16% of the world's population is young people between 15 and 24 years old [1], if we count it up to 30 years old, according to our calculations, it will increase from 16% to 34%. In Uzbekistan, they make up almost 22 percent of the population, and 31 percent if we count those under 30 years old. In any case, young people differ among socio-demographic strata not only in their number, but also in their attitude to the environment, changes in society, creative activity and tendency to support innovations. Young minds tend to accept updates as a natural state, an objective necessity. However, in most young people, passivity, desire for convenience, and consumerism are the priority. It's no secret that some young people are involved in activities such as joining terrorists, criminal groups, drug addiction, and the desire to make quick, easy money. As society changes in a positive direction, such inhumane and immoral events become more visible.

Science and intellectuals are encouraged to find the objective and subjective foundations of such phenomena, to form positive social qualities in young people, to make them creative and active individuals. Cultural-mass events, performances are a form of activity with specific goals and objectives, which affect a wide audience, public unity, and all individuals regardless of age, gender, and views. Such events unite the masses around certain ideas, values, ethno-cultural traditions, create in their minds "life goals" capable of self-education and formation, teach them to effectively use their creative power and opportunities. Artistic and aesthetic means and methods of events enrich the mind with new impressions, ideas and thoughts, encourage a person to show creative activity and live creatively. This aesthetic-psychological factor in cultural and public events can sometimes change the consciousness of a person to a completely different direction, and form a new social ideal in him. This process is two-way, that is, the organizer, director, and actor of the event together with the mass audience gain spiritual and life experience, sharpen their thoughts and views. The formation of social consciousness takes place on the basis of such interaction, dialogue, and cooperation. At the time, K. Stanislavsky called it "cooperation of creative research" and considered it a factor that motivates the artist to work on himself [2, p. 34-35]. True, there are differences between theater art and its audience and cultural-public events and their audience. Cultural and mass events imply maximum activation of the audience, i.e. turning them into a full-fledged subject of the event, in theater art a certain distance is maintained between the actor and the recipient. Consciousness is a complex psychological reality, it is influenced by many factors. Cultural and public events should take into account the multiplicity of youth consciousness. For example, the flexibility and fluctuating (wave-like) formation of the youth mind prompts the organizer of the event to choose a theme, episode, song, actors' actions that are universal, suitable for all sensitive experiences. At this point, it is not enough to consider artistic and aesthetic interest. To clearly know the ideas and ideals in the minds of young people, to plan in which direction they can be changed, requires great experience and aesthetic-psychological knowledge.

The role and importance of creating a creative environment that helps actualize the mind's own "I" is especially important. Because, as the doctor of philosophy, professor S. Norkulov wrote, "The "I" in the mind and its "self-actualization" do not take place in a dry place, it needs a social space, an environment. At this point, the "I" in the mind, its "self-actualization" and the social consciousness creativity, creative, creative features are combined" [3, p. 32].

In the "I" of young minds, on the one hand, there is an intereative, even egoistic tendency, and on the other hand, exereotive, that is, selflessness, altruism. These characteristics confirm the fluctuating formation of the mind of young people. Cultural and public events fulfill their social function by turning "I" into "We". The phenomenon of "I" expresses maximalism and interreotivity in young people, and its sharp form expresses egoism and arrogance. The transformation of "I" into "We" is rooted in a better awareness of the forms and manifestations of interpersonal tendencies. Even the most impressive artistic-aesthetic activities, images and methods may not be able to change the intereative inclinations. In this place, the importance of personal psychological factors and experiences becomes incomparable. For example, today most young people attend mosques because of this personal spiritual factor and the influence of experiences. No one organizes them to go to these religious events, they are not invited by special advertisements, but their personal spiritual needs motivate them to attend mosques. The perception of cultural and public events in the minds of young people is more clearly demonstrated as a result of the following questions and answers. Our "What is the impact of cultural and public events on the minds of young people is reflected more?" to our question, 49% of our respondents answered "in their relationship to life", 43% in their "creative thinking", 34% in their "interest in art", 20% in their "scientific and worldly views", 16% in their "formation of national thinking", 7% in their "patriotism", 4% in their "international is interested in the problems of life" answered. Among the answers, "relationship with life" takes the leading place (49 percent).

"Attitude to life" is a broad concept, it is a set of ideas about the environment, social existence, society and human behavior. Of course, it is a positive thing that cultural and public events can instill such a philosophical attitude to life. Such relationships formed in the minds of young people make them socially active, creative approachers to life, and people who strive to further improve social existence. Such an active attitude to social existence is the result of the positive views, imagination and ideals formed in the minds of young people. Among the answers, "creative thinking" (43 percent) takes the second place. This answer should be interpreted broadly. "Creative thinking" includes the search for the positive, a critical approach, and striving to expand and enrich existing approaches. Critical thinking characteristic of young people has been known for a long time. Maximalism in them sometimes turns radical, as a result of which there is a danger of creative thinking turning into nihilism. Therefore, in cultural and public events, more young people are addressed to the topics that form positive views, great attention is paid to the use of images, artifacts and symbols. Creative thinking prepares young people to be creative, to search for new ideas, to create something. It is not for nothing that Eastern mystics (Buddha, Hamadoni, Naqshband) paid great attention to the formation of human thinking. They left the saying that your mind is yours. A creatively thinking recipient correctly understands the creative processes, looks favorably on the artist's experiences. This alone indicates that a confident view of cultural and public events was formed in his mind. "Interest in art" (34 percent) takes the next place among the answers.

All types and forms of literature, music, dance, visual arts, performances, cinema, and artistic-aesthetic creativity are syncretized in cultural-public events. It is this aspect that makes cultural and public events universal, popular and enjoyable. Interest in art in young people prepares the ground for expressing one's creative self. The sociological essence of interest is when it motivates a person to work and search. Curiosity becomes objectified in activities and pursuits and expresses goals in the mind. Cultural-public events unite the interests of the audience around artistic-aesthetic ideas and compositions, bring personal life goals in "I" close to the concept of "We". The influence of scientific-secular views (20 percent) on the life of young people is of fundamental importance for all sciences dealing with the phenomenon of consciousness. Special emphasis should be placed on this factor in order for the organization of cultural and public events to be a scientific-worldly view, activity, and art form. New Uzbekistan needs young people with scientific and worldly views, innovative and creative thinking. The leadership and government

of our republic have adopted national culture and concepts for innovative development of our country for 2030.

It is emphasized in them that one of the strategic tasks is to educate young people who have mastered the secrets of modern science, culture and art [4; 5; 6]. Formation of scientific and worldly views in young people, organization of educational, promotional, cultural and public works in accordance with these concepts and decisions is entrusted to culture and art workers. Today, it is very difficult to assess the processes in the field of culture and art, the level of organized cultural and public events, and the artistic and aesthetic value. In this regard, criteria supporting creative research have not yet been created or developed. Therefore, intuitive assessment of cultural and mass events is widespread today, not in accordance with scientific tests. Here it becomes clear that scientific research and theory lag behind practice. The construction of cultural and public events based on scientific and worldly views is a requirement of social development. The need and interest in such events is great among the youth audience. In this place, art mysticism, artistic fantasy, plots and spectacles that play on the imagination have a great influence. However, in our opinion, they should not be absolute. No matter how many elements of mysticism and irrationality there are in art, it cannot live apart from real existence and demands of social life. Symbols, artefacts and symbols, background, screen, sound, images and slogans used in cultural and public events are effective when they awaken imaginations of real life problems in the minds of young people. "Vitality is an attribute of art" [5.27-29 p.]. So, we have the right to demand vitality, scientific-secularity from cultural-mass events. Cultural-mass events are organized in a certain ethno-cultural space and based on ethno-cultural traditions. Formation of national thinking in the minds of young people is one of the main tasks of cultural and public events. National thinking is a reality consisting of knowledge, views and imaginations of a person about his people, nation. This reality is not formed mechanically by belonging to the people, the nation.

It requires special educational, educational, cultural and public events. That's why 20 percent of our respondents say that cultural and public events form national thinking in the minds of young people. National thinking deterministically forms ideas about people, nation, ethnoculture, language, customs, traditions, heritage in the minds of young people. Therefore, he has the opportunity to understand and evaluate the entire ethno-cultural wealth. 7% of our respondents indicate that cultural and public events form patriotic feelings in the minds of young people. At first glance, this answer may raise questions. Is the sense of country less than interest in art? Or are there other reasons and motives hidden in such an answer? In any case, the formation of a sense of patriotism occupies an important place in the system of cultural and public events for young people. The interest of young people in the problems of international life (4 percent) is not much taken into account in cultural and public events. Young people seek to satisfy their interest not through cultural-public events, but through the Internet. From the above comments and the analysis of respondents' answers, it is clear that cultural-public events have the potential to creatively influence the minds of young people as syncretic creativity and art, as a form of activity. This creative influence is first of all reflected in young people's creative attitude to life, interest in art, directing "I" to "We", in short, realizing their inner potential. The conflicting and fluctuating character of consciousness requires to constantly study the interests of young people, to organize cultural and public events in accordance with this dynamic phenomenon.

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